

SARS-CoV-2: Navigating information overload with Lens.org

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Brief description

Evidence must be used to guide interventions for the COVID-19 pandemic, but that evidence must be comprehensive, credible and shared for it to be effective. This report focuses on how global scientific research and patenting activity relevant to SARS-CoV-2, including its genetics and pathogenesis, can be discovered and made transparent, open, shareable and navigable to help inform how it could be translated into intervention options.

We demonstrate how the platform Lens.org can be used to conduct reliable systematic scholarly and patent searches, refine and build domain-based collections to share publicly, and set alerts to receive notifications for updates. We also provide some analyses/comments on some of these collections. Our aim is to enable researchers to find clarity into the discovery, analysis, and translation of COVID-19 scientific and patent knowledge into products, practices or services to help mitigate the current crisis.

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Overview

First described and reported from Wuhan, China, SARS-CoV-2 rages on across more than 188 countries now, having caused over [898,000 confirmed deaths](#) since January 2020. In the previous Lens report, we introduced this virus in the context of other human coronaviruses and here, we use the Lens global, open knowledge resources to quickly assemble, expose, and map the wealth of information accumulated over the past 9 months about its genetic structure, dynamics of its replication, spread, and management.

Two critical corpora of highly-related knowledge are essential to combine and meld into evidence-based guidance: global research findings in the scholarly literature and patent disclosures. Both of these bodies of knowledge have been constrained by limited access and reuse and/or by surveillance of users' activity. Both of these business strategies compromise effective public action and trust..

As patents or genetic sequences disclosed in patents can offer unique insights into attempts to solve similar viral problems and which may require more than science, but also engagement by enterprise and coordinated partnerships to manufacture or produce interventions, we create and share patent and patent sequence collections associated with selected interventions proposed recently by the community to expose evidence on what is known and unknown about this virus and the disease it causes. Besides detailed descriptions of inventions, patents can expose what rights exist, which countries or inventions have no constraints, who or which entity is pursuing them, which institutions or companies may have capabilities to make the products and practice the changes we need, and which research informs and strengthens these interventions.

By making patent literature fully discoverable and linking it to scholarly work that is cited by and informs the inventions, with links through to the open access forms where available, we hope this growing Lens Report can begin to build bridges to solutions.

While patent applications are typically only published 18 months after filing, and the virus only emerged about 9 months ago, we do not expect to see Covid-19 specific patents appearing for some time. However virtually all the strategies being used to develop interventions will be based on existing technologies and platforms, and for these legal rights and practical use know-how must be dealt with. Also, the close relationship between the current pandemic virus and previous outbreaks of coronavirus disease will illuminate and inform actions being taken now, by improved practices and public health measures.

What is this report about?

Raging across societies, nations and environments, SARS-CoV-2, the etiologic agent of COVID-19 pandemic, has devastated the health and well-being of millions and slowed down the global economy. Due to its novel nature and extraordinary impact on daily life, it requires a rapid and effective response, informed by earlier global public health knowledge, but with new or improved strategies specific for this virus and the urgency of its impact. Patents specifically targeted to developing specific vaccines, diagnostics, therapeutics or prophylactics to this new agent will not appear until at least 18 months after the initial observation of the outbreak. Thus, using Lens' mining of preprints and emerging academic research in addition to collections may shed some light onto the latest and old science that could inform such new products. However, we need to use some judgment calls to know which is likely to inform work by the private sector. It may be that historical influence of particular types of research, or even researchers, groups or institutions on the patenting process could be a useful guide.

In this dynamic report, we provide a brief overview on knowns and unknowns of SARS-CoV-2 evolutionary genetic relationship to bat and other human coronaviruses, its population genetics and spread dynamics, and its possible modes of entry into the human host. We then link that information to emerging diagnostics and varied immune responses observed in patients and how they may impact antiviral therapies that have now entered clinical trials. Out of 167 vaccine candidates, we analyze the 29 candidates that are in clinical evaluation and which WHO has recently listed from around the globe. We also shed some light on the drug, biological, dietary supplement, and prophylactic therapeutic interventions that are in the recruiting stage of various clinical trial phases.

We also provide a key element that may be crucial to success: biological sequences - DNA, protein and RNA - that are disclosed in the patent literature - that may be crucial for developing rapid and accurate diagnostics, therapeutics or vaccines. As researchers are sharing the sequences of the new virus variants openly and publicly, in this report, we also expose preliminary sequence similarity analyses on selected viral protein components to illuminate what potential detection methods, diagnostic assays or vaccines are in the pipeline or already available for coronaviruses or what region of the genome is of particular interest for other treatment options.

Description of the scholarly and patent collections used throughout the report pages can be found in the sources tab and all these collections are publicly accessible and will be soon downloadable from Lens.org

SARS-CoV-2 is an enveloped, positive sense, single-stranded RNA coronavirus

The virus belongs to the subgenus *Sabercovirus* of the betacoronaviruses genus in the Coronaviridae family. Betacoronaviruses infect both humans and mammals. The first internationally reported novel SARS-CoV-2 isolate (Reference sequence) was from Wuhan (Human isolate 1) by [Wu et al, 2020](#). Coronaviruses have the largest genomes among RNA viruses, that of SARS-Cov-2 comprises around 30kb organized into genes encoding

structural (Spike protein, Membrane protein, Envelope protein, and Nucleocapsid protein) and non structural proteins (nsp1-16). Using deep sequencing techniques, various alignment tools, and population genetics analyses, scientists found possible recombination events that may have led to having 2/3 of the SARS-CoV-2 genome as a mixture from various "paternal" viruses.

Fig. 1 | Genome organization of SARS and SARS-like CoVs. The organization of genes for WHCV, bat SL-CoVZC45 and SARS-CoV Tor2.

[Wu et al., 2020](#)

What is the role of recombination in the evolution of SARS-CoV-2?

In general, recombination is thought to be an important evolutionary mechanism for RNA viruses as it enables them to get rid of deleterious mutations, introduced by error-prone replication, to adapt, and to survive in various environments. In light of the evidence presented in [these published works](#), recombination events are common in SARS-CoV-2, most likely have led to its emergence from horseshoe bats, genus *Rhinolophus*, and are ongoing in critical viral protein regions. Initially the receptor binding domain (RBD) in the spike protein was highlighted as the recombination hotspot, further work though demonstrated that S1/S2 cleavage site in the spike protein, ORF8 and DUF3655 position within ORF1ab are other hotspots worthy of our attention as well. Considering the important role RBD plays in virus entry into human cells and the urgency to find effective therapies, more efforts were devoted to better understand the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 and the mechanism of its interaction with human cells ([Huang et al., 2020](#) and [Zhou et al., 2020](#)). Molecular characterizations of the RBD of RmYN02 and the representative beta-CoVs along with SARS-CoV-2 showed that the virus is closer to RmYN02 than RaTG13, and divergence from RmYN02 is from at least 26 years ago, and both diverged from RaTG13 at least 37 years ago.

have little or no effect on the function of the gene. Most often these are single changes (SNPs - single nucleotide polymorphisms), and where the nucleotide change does not change an encoded amino acid (silent sites) [Yin, 2020](#).

Lens scholarly collection, [SARS-CoV-2: Recombination and mutation](#)

To facilitate deeper analyses of scholarly works targeting recombination and mutation of SARS-CoV-2, we created a public Lens collection: [SARS-CoV-2: Recombination and mutation collection](#) based on this search: *(title:(SARS-CoV-2) OR abstract:(SARS-CoV-2) OR fulltext:(SARS-CoV-2)) AND (title:(\"COVID-19\") OR abstract:(\"COVID-19\") OR fulltext:(\"COVID-19\")) AND (title:(\"recombination\") OR abstract:(\"recombination\") OR fulltext:(\"recombination\")) AND (title:(\"mutation\") OR abstract:(\"mutation\") OR fulltext:(\"mutation\"))* as we scanned and read some of these articles, we examined their citations and added manually any further work that we found relevant. Predominantly, the collection contains works on the role of recombination in the emergence and persistence of SARS-CoV-2 and it will be a dynamic Lens collection (auto updated with each lens data update).

By March 2020, recombination and specific mutation events in betacoronaviruses were recognized as most likely the cause for the emergence of SARS-CoV-2 in 2019 from bats. Expanding on these findings, [Rodríguez-Román and Gibbs, 2020](#) found that, in SARS-CoV-2 and its relatives, mutations occur throughout the genome, but most recombination events are confined to the 3' end of the genomes. In SARS-CoV-2, this involved both the Spike protein and ORF8, although changes in its DUF3655 region may have resulted from mutation and selection.

During normal replication of betacoronaviruses, RNA recombination is required for subgenomic mRNA synthesis, a process that generates defective viral genome populations. Published works from [Mark Denison's lab](#) demonstrated that SARS-CoV-2, like other betacoronaviruses, performs extensive and high-frequency recombination and generates diverse species of recombined RNAs during replication. And while the role of the 3'-5' riboexonuclease (nsp14-EXON), which mediates proofreading mechanism during the subgenomic RNA synthesis in other coronaviruses, was determined, we still do not understand the role of nsp14 in SARS-CoV-2 replication fidelity of the error-prone RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) mediated replication. Similarly, the significance of recombination or mutation events on virus infectivity, survival, or treatment of COVID-19 patients is still lacking.

Using single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) to compare isolates, [Yin, 2020](#) was able to trace and genotype mutations from 558 viral genome sequences reported from around the world (by March 23, 2020). Mutations were found at a few fixed positions in critical virus proteins, such as the 23403A>G mutation in spike glycoprotein (S protein, D614G), 14408C>T in RNA dependent RNA polymerase

(nsp12, P323L), 28144T>C in RNA primase (nsp8, L84S) and 28881G>A (R203K), 28882G>A (R202R), or 28883G>C (G204R) mutations in nucleocapsid phosphoprotein (N).

Recombination and Mutation

Analysis dashboard of the Lens scholarly collection: SARS-CoV-2: Recombination and Mutation

Below, we present a Lens dashboard for this collection to allow exploration of the authors associated with this line of research, their co-author networks, and the affiliated institutions/countries involved.

Authors associated with "coronavirus recombination and mutation" research

Aggregated works per institution with co-authorship profiles

This chart shows the top authors in the most active institutions in this result set, based on number of scholarly works. This chart type allows you to view one facet broken down by another facet. For example the top authors per institution or top journals per country, etc. Depending on your data, this might be better suited as either a grouped or stacked bar chart. You can also try swapping the facets.

Countries of the affiliated institutional works

This chart shows the top institutions in the top countries/regions based on number of scholarly works in this result set. This chart type allows you to view one facet broken down by another facet. For example the top authors per institution or top journals per country, etc. Depending on your data, this might be better suited as either a grouped or stacked bar chart. You can also try swapping the facets.

Research funders information found

This chart shows the top institutional funding recipients by funding agency for this result set, based on the number of scholarly works. This chart type allows you to view one facet broken down by another facet. For example the top authors per institution or top journals per country, etc. Depending on your data, this might be better suited as either a grouped or stacked bar chart. You can also try swapping the facets.

Open access status of top published works in these journals

This chart shows the number of scholarly works by open access status for the top journals/source titles in this result set, based on number of scholarly works. This chart type allows you to view one facet broken down by another facet. For example the top authors per institution or top journals per country, etc. Depending on your data, this might be better suited as either a grouped or stacked bar chart. You can also try swapping the facets.

Open access status of works for the top publishers in this collection

This chart shows the relative proportion of open access scholarly works for the top publishers in this result set by the number of scholarly works. This chart type allows you to view one facet broken down by another facet. For example the top authors per institution or top journals per country, etc. Depending on your data, this might be better suited as either a grouped or stacked bar chart. You can also try swapping the facets.

Virus Variants

How do SARS-CoV-2 genome variants spread around the globe?

Evidence is accumulating that specific mutations, generated at a few fixed positions in critical viral proteins, assist SARS-CoV-2 in spreading and adapting to diverse populations across the globe. Building on [Yin, 2020](#)'s genotyping works of 558 viral genome sequences, [Toyoshima et al., 2020](#) clustered 12,343 genome sequences from patients across 28 countries relative to the reference isolate from Wuhan (accession number MN908947) and investigated associations with increased fatality in populations pre-vaccinated with bacille Calmette-Guerin (BCG), a vaccine for tuberculosis disease, or human leukocyte antigen (HLA), cell surface proteins responsible for regulating human immune system. While the authors identified significant associations of some virus genome variants with mortality rates, further evidence is still needed to establish a cause and effect relationship. On the other hand, [Nakashima et al.](#) followed the single amino acid (D614G) shift in the Spike protein in 1500-2000 nucleotide and protein sequences submitted to National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) with date and location metadata prior to March 2020 and showed that such a mutation may have occurred at the same time across various places suggesting that the mutation may have originated from a single source.

SARS-CoV-2 genomic variations associated with mortality rate of COVID-19

Fig. 1 Clustering analysis of SARS-CoV-2 among 28 countries. **a** Heatmap for the frequencies of SARS-CoV-2 mutants. The 28 countries were classified into three clusters based on the mutational signature by a hierarchical clustering. Protein sequence based on the SARS-CoV-2_Wuhan-Hu-1 sequence (GenBank accession number

MN908947) is used as a reference. Ref; amino acid in reference SARS-CoV-2 sequence, Mut, amino acid in mutant SARS-CoV-2. **b** A global mapping of the three clusters. **c** Fatality rates according to the clusters. Horizontal lines represent the means. The Student's *t* test was used to evaluate statistical significance

[Toyoshima et al., 2020](#)

Figure 6. GAU-to-GGU conversion was detected all over the world.

a, Monthly timeline of the newly added specimens carrying GAU and GGU nucleotide mutations in the world and the continents. The data sampled in China was separately shown, where a state of emergency has been practically lifted. The data in April was not registered (NR) in China. GGU conversion was not registered in China. The specimen numbers are shown in a logarithmic scale. No other codons for D614G were found. See Supplementary Data Source for the detailed names of the countries.

[Nakashima et al, 2020](#)

[Korber et al, 2020](#) expanded further the study on the D614G mutation by accessing 28,576 spike sequences submitted to the Global Initiative for Sharing All Influenza Data (GISAID) database, in particular the SARS-CoV-2 submitted sequences by May 29, 2020, and tracked mutations also across space and over time.

While Nakashima et al.'s findings showed that the mutation took place in February, 2020 with no records from China, Korber et al found that at that time there were only a few samples from Asia showing the mutation but the initial mutation was predominantly in Europe. Spread of that mutation has accelerated since March across Europe-Africa, Americas and the rest of the world showing how in time the two variants have persisted in the various regions based on the relative frequency of sampled genome sequences in the database.

[Korber et al, 2020](#)

These results confirm that similar and even identical mutations both at amino-acid and nucleotide resolutions are possible in SARS-CoV-2 patients and are ongoing. Moreover, [studies from China, Spain, France and Italy](#) confirmed the presence of complex and dynamic distributions of closely related variants in samples from single COVID-19 patients. While we take note of them, their role in virus transmissibility and pathogenesis is not clear yet.

Considering that SARS-CoV-2 has a much smaller genome than its new human host, there is no surprise that it can rapidly produce a large cloud of variants from a few parental genotypes. As with

other RNA viruses, SARS-CoV-2 seems to also have a high mutation frequency in COVID-19 patients. According to [Holland, 2006](#), these unique RNA virus characteristics require a "quasispecies" concept for meaningful insights; "RNA virus diseases always involve complex *quasispecies populations*, not "a virus" or "a virus mutant," which has been selected because it is "the fittest." This understanding, I think, will need to guide any therapeutics or vaccine design for COVID-19.

As the three presented examples in this page show that there is no stable and consistent "wild type" virus rather than most likely there are mutant clouds that change over time and space as well as depending on the age of the human host, ethnic background, pre-existing health conditions and seasonal temperatures, such a mutant cloud may shift in proportion or density.

Korber et al. showed that the D614G mutation is almost always accompanied by three other mutations: "a C-to-T mutation in the 5' UTR (position 241 relative to the Wuhan reference sequence), a silent C-to-T mutation at position 3,037, and a C-to-T mutation at position 14,408 that results in an amino acid change in the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp P323L)." These results suggest that more than one species of RNA is present in the host and support the single nucleotide mutation frequency analyses that [Yin, 2020] (<http://export.arxiv.org/pdf/2003.10965>) conducted and which showed that SARS-CoV-2 can have a high mutation frequency rate per nucleotide.

Structural and simulation models predict that the D614G mutation in the spike protein leads to higher binding affinity with the host receptor ([Mansbach et al, 2020](#)) which can also explain the versatility and plasticity of virus variants to adapt in different environments to its host and may inform that a mixture of antibodies with various degrees of neutralization capability to the virus receptor binding domain may be more effective and have a better chance in controlling the virus at the entry level.

Considering that diverse mutations in the virus genome are generated during replication but mutation events seem to be restricted to a few key positions within critical proteins, suggest there may be a limit to the error rate that SARS-CoV-2 can tolerate during replication to maintain itself in the host. This limit was referred to by other scientists ([see Holland, 2006 for more references](#)) as *the error threshold* and its value is based on the overall complexity of the information encoded by the other viral components. Holland speculated that coronaviruses, having the largest genome size among other RNA viruses (27-31 kb) may display a higher average replication fidelity compared to other smaller RNA viral genomes and this is mainly due to a nuclease domain in the genome that provides a proofreading-repair function during coronavirus replication. This is an area that is not yet clear for SARS-CoV-2.

[Grubaugh et al.](#) expressed caution in over interpreting the meaning of D614G mutation and whether such a single mutation will change the outcome of an infection, or a pandemic but [Benedetti et al., 2020](#), on the other hand, speculated that such change may be signaling a march towards adaptation rather than increased virulence based on our previous understanding of coronaviruses. In any case,

we all await more evidence on the direct association of virus variants with increased infectivity or mortality in COVID-19 patients. In the next section, we will introduce the genetic structure and organization of Spike protein and then look on how this important protein interacts with the human host cells to mediate and facilitate virus entry and infection.

Spike Protein Characteristics

Linking the scientific and patent knowledge on SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein

The Spike protein is an envelope surface-located glycoprotein that is critical for viral attachment, fusion, and entry into host cells. Recent studies by [Zhou et al., 2020](#) and [Wang et al., 2020](#) found that the spike protein binds strongly to human angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (hACE2) receptor to facilitate virus entry, similar to SARS-CoV1 and human coronavirus NL63 (hCoV-NL63), but the binding affinity in SARS-CoV-2 to the hACE2 receptor is 4 fold stronger compared with SARS-CoV-1 receptor binding domain (RBD). Hence the Spike protein has become widely targeted in the development of antibody-mediated neutralization, inhibitors of viral entry, and vaccine efforts.

To learn more about the annotated regions in SARS-CoV-2 spike protein (Wuhan-H1 isolate, GenBank accession number MN908947) that are relevant and similar to other coronaviruses, we performed a BLASTP search using the non redundant protein database at the public facility of National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) site. Search results of the query Spike protein produced significant alignments to other coronaviruses' spike proteins. Putative conservative domains have also been detected in BLAST results and a list of domain hits determined. Recognizing the location of these domains, we then performed various sequence similarity searches including that of the whole spike protein in the Lens PatSeq Finder to check whether there were any sequence listing disclosures made in the patent literature and by whom.

List of domain hits

Hit	Name	Accession	Description	Interval	E-value
[+]	Corona_S2	pfam01601	Coronavirus S2 glycoprotein; The coronavirus spike glycoprotein forms the characteristic ...	662-1270	0e+00
[+]	SARS-CoV-2_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21480	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 ...	319-541	6.60e-166
[+]	SARS-CoV-like_Spike_S1_NTD	cd21624	N-terminal domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from Severe acute respiratory ...	13-304	3.77e-152
[+]	SARS-CoV-like_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21477	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of severe acute respiratory syndrome-related ...	319-541	3.72e-136
[+]	SARS-CoV_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21481	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of severe acute respiratory syndrome-related ...	319-541	5.29e-115
[+]	Spike_rec_bind	pfam09408	Spike receptor binding domain; Spike is an envelope glycoprotein which aids viral entry into ...	330-583	4.39e-79
[+]	CoV_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21470	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of coronavirus spike (S) proteins; This family ...	320-526	1.98e-72
[+]	CoV_Spike_S1_NTD	cd21527	N-terminal domain of the S1 subunit of coronavirus Spike (S) proteins; This family contains ...	34-301	4.28e-49
[+]	batCoV-HKU9-like_Spike_S1_NTD	cd21627	N-terminal domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from Rousettus bat coronavirus ...	192-301	2.24e-08
[+]	HCoV-OC43-like_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21485	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from human coronavirus OC43 ...	318-437	3.38e-08
[+]	HEV_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21508	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from porcine ...	316-437	1.04e-07
[+]	HKU1-like_CoV_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21478	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from human coronavirus HKU1 ...	316-432	2.41e-07
[+]	bat_HKU4-like_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21487	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from Tylonycteris bat ...	320-473	1.65e-06
[+]	MHV-like_Spike_S1_NTD	cd21625	N-terminal domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from murine hepatitis virus and ...	265-301	2.56e-06
[+]	HKU1_N1_CoV_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21483	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from human coronavirus HKU1, ...	316-450	3.92e-06
[+]	MHV-like_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21484	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from mouse hepatitis virus ...	316-432	5.90e-06
[+]	HKU1_N5-like_CoV_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21482	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from human coronavirus HKU1, ...	316-450	9.90e-06
[+]	MERS-CoV-like_Spike_S1_NTD	cd21626	N-terminal domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from Middle East respiratory ...	246-302	1.69e-05
[+]	MERS-like_CoV_Spike_S1_RBD	cd21479	receptor-binding domain of the S1 subunit of the Spike (S) protein from Middle East ...	320-499	3.76e-05

Blast search parameters

Data Source: Live blast search RID = JUWUBJR9014
 User Options: Database: CDSEARCH/cdd Low complexity filter: no Composition Based Adjustment: yes E-value threshold: 0.01 Maximum number of hits: 500

Patent sequence search similarity results for SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein

To interpret, understand, and value the combined effect of a genetic sequence on a biological invention, the Lens provides an application, PatSeq Finder, that allows sequence-based similarity searches within the context of almost all known patent sequence disclosures to date. And by linking that information to that from the scientific literature, we can predict contextual uses in patents and potential products that are in the pipeline. Here, we show sequence similarity search results on the whole spike protein and identify three patent owners, Amgen Inc, Academia Sinica, and Crucell Holland BV who have referenced sequences similar to SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in their granted patent claims. More details on these granted patents and other patent applications are below.

Spike protein: Wuhan-Hu1 20200806 Start another search

Results

Query: MFVFLVLLPLVSSQCVNLTTRTQLPPAYTNSFTRGVYYPD... (Length: 1273aa) ▶ Show summary of result average and medians

Location in document Grants, in claims (4) ● Grants (4) ● Applications, in claims (0) ● Applications (0) ●

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 filtered hits - 500 total hits *

Sequence	Coverage	Similarity	Alignment length	E-value	BLAST score	Patent number	<input type="checkbox"/>
SEQ ID 115 US 8106170 B2 Sequence length: 1,255aa	100%	76.0%	1,277aa	0	2,037.69 bits	US 8106170 B2 Public collections:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Compositions against SARS-coronavirus and uses thereof

US, Published Jan 31, 2012, Filed Nov 10, 2005
Applicants: TER MEULEN JAN HENRIK, VAN DEN BRINK EDWARD NORBERT, DE KRUIF CORNELIS ADRIAN, GOUDSMIT JAAP, CRUCELL HOLLAND BV
Organism: Artificial

[View and track results in the Lens](#)

Which patents have disclosed similar sequences to the Spike protein in their Claims based on the 20200806 search results in PatSeq Finder?

Granted patents

Recombinant Baculovirus And Virus-like Particle
Published: May 5, 2009 Filed: Nov 24, 2004 Earliest Priority: Nov 25, 2003
Applicant: ACADEMIA SINICA
Family: 4 Cited Works: 2 Cited by: 20 Cites: 4

Granted Patent US 7527967 B2 085-250-666-990-457

Antibodies To Sars Coronavirus
Published: Jun 1, 2010 Filed: May 21, 2007 Earliest Priority: May 19, 2006
Applicant: AMGEN INC
Family: 11 Cited Works: 51 Cited by: 6 Cites: 9

Granted Patent US 7728110 B2 064-729-277-368-413

Compositions Against Sars-coronavirus And Uses Thereof
Published: Jan 31, 2012 Filed: Nov 10, 2005 Earliest Priority: Nov 11, 2004
Applicant: TER MEULEN JAN HENRIK, VAN DEN BRINK EDWARD NORBERT, DE KRUIF CORNELIS ADRIAN, GOUDSMIT JAAP, CRUCELL HOLLAND BV
Family: 17 Cited Works: 53 Cited by: 20 Cites: 17

Granted Patent US 8106170 B2 017-213-287-455-965

[View as Lens result](#)

Patent applications sorted by family size

<p>Use Of Proteins And Peptides Encoded By The Genome Of A Novel Sars-associated Coronavirus Strain</p> <p>Published: Nov 29, 2007 Filed: Dec 2, 2004 Earliest Priority: Dec 2, 2003 Applicant: VAN DER WERF SYLVIE, ESCRIOU NICOLAS, CRESCENZO-CHAIGNE BERNADETTE, MANUQUERRA JEAN-CLAUDE, KUNST FREDERICK, BETTON JEAN-MICHEL, GERBAUD SYLVIE, BURGUERRE ANA M, AZEBI SALIMA, CHARNIELA PIERRE, TANGY FREDERIC, COMBREDET CHANTAL, DELAGNEAU JEAN-FRANCOIS, MARTIN MONIQUE Family: 32 Cited Works: 0 Cited by: 2 Citex: 2</p> <p>Patent Application US 2007/0278002 A1 021-442-287-094-77X</p>
<p>Respiratory Virus Vaccines</p> <p>Published: Apr 27, 2017 Filed: Oct 21, 2016 Earliest Priority: Oct 22, 2015 Applicant: MODERNA TX INC Family: 126 Cited Works: 0 Cited by: 9 Citex: 0</p> <p>Patent Application WO 2017/070828 A2 123-983-497-176-709</p>
<p>The Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus</p> <p>Published: Oct 26, 2004 Filed: Apr 9, 2004 Earliest Priority: Apr 10, 2003 Applicant: CHIRON CORP, RAPPULOJI RINDU, MABIGNANI VEGA, STADLER KONRAD, GREGERSEN JENS-PETER, CHEN DAVID, HAN JANG, POLO JOHN, WEINER AMY, HOUGHTON MICHAEL, SONG HYUN CHUL, SEO MI YOUNG, DONNELLY JOHN J, KLENK HANS DIETER, VALKANTE NICHOLAS Family: 15 Cited Works: 13 Cited by: 60 Citex: 14</p> <p>Patent Application WO 2004/092380 A2 060-378-159-234-557</p>
<p>Inhibitors Based On Fusion, Hr1 And Hr2 Sequences In Bacterial Adhesin</p> <p>Published: Jan 19, 2006 Filed: Jul 6, 2005 Earliest Priority: Jul 6, 2004 Applicant: CHIRON SRL, MABIGNANI VEGA Family: 14 Cited Works: 0 Cited by: 1 Citex: 0</p> <p>Patent Application WO 2006/008074 A2 176-521-429-667-878</p>
<p>Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Dna Vaccine Compositions And Methods Of Use</p> <p>Published: May 10, 2007 Filed: May 11, 2004 Earliest Priority: May 16, 2003 Applicant: VICAL INC Family: 11 Cited Works: 0 Cited by: 39 Citex: 53</p> <p>Patent Application US 2007/0106190 A1 038-928-588-935-981</p>

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What claims have been granted based on SARS-CoV-1 work?

Recombinant Baculovirus And Virus-like Particle

Published: May 5, 2009 Earliest Priority: Nov 25 2003 Family: 4 Cited Works: 2 Cited by: 20 Cites: 4 Sequences: 25
Additional Info: [Cited Works](#) [Full text](#)

Summary Full-text Cites 2 Works Cited By 20 Patents Cites 4 Patents Family Info Sequences Legal Info Collections Notes 4

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Abstract
Recombinant baculoviruses, virus-like particles, and polypeptide that contain a protein sequence of a heterologous virus, related compositions, and related preparation, screening, delivery, detection, and treatment methods.

Claims

1. A recombinant baculovirus comprising a fusion heterologous polypeptide that contains a baculoviral envelope-targeting sequence, wherein the heterologous polypeptide is located on the surface of the baculovirus and the baculoviral envelope-targeting sequence consists of SEQ ID NO: 9.
2. The recombinant baculovirus of claim 1, wherein the heterologous polypeptide contains the sequence of a polypeptide of a heterologous virus.
3. The recombinant baculovirus of claim 2, wherein the heterologous virus is a coronavirus.
4. The recombinant baculovirus of claim 3, wherein the coronavirus virus is a severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus.
5. The recombinant baculovirus of claim 3, wherein the heterologous polypeptide contains the sequence of the envelope protein, membrane protein, nucleocapsid protein, or spike protein of the coronavirus, or an antigenic fragment thereof.
6. The recombinant baculovirus of claim 5, wherein the heterologous polypeptide contains one of SEQ ID NOs: 1-8, or an antigenic fragment thereof.
7. The recombinant baculovirus of claim 5, wherein the heterologous polypeptide

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Owners (US)
 Academia Sinica
Executed: Dec 13, 2004

US Classifications
435/320.1 424/211.1 424/221.1

Applicants
Academia Sinica

IPC Classifications
C12N1/00 A61K39/12 A61K39/155 A61K39/215 C07H21/04 C07K14/11
C07K14/165 C12N7/00 C12N7/01 C12N7/04 C12N15/113 C12N15/866
C12P21/04 C12Q1/70 G01N33/50

Inventors
Chao Yu-chan , Liu Yen-yen

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Antibodies To Sars Coronavirus

Published: Jun 1, 2010 Earliest Priority: May 19 2006 Family: 11 Cited Works: 51 Cited by: 6 Cites: 9 Sequences: 134
Additional Info: [Cited Works](#) [Full text](#)

Summary Full-text Cites 51 Works Cited By 6 Patents Cites 9 Patents Family Info Sequences Legal Info Collections Notes 4

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Abstract
The present invention relates to antibodies including human antibodies and antigen-binding portions thereof that specifically bind to human SARS-CoV S protein, and that function to neutralize SARS-CoV. The invention also relates to antibodies that are bispecific, derivatized, single chain antibodies or portions of fusion proteins. The invention also relates to isolated heavy and light chain immunoglobulins derived from human anti-SARS-CoV S protein antibodies and nucleic acid molecules encoding such immunoglobulins. The present invention also relates to methods of using the antibodies and compositions for diagnosis and treatment. The invention also provides gene therapy methods using nucleic acid molecules encoding the heavy and/or light immunoglobulin molecules that comprise the human anti-SARS-CoV S protein antibodies. The invention also relates to transgenic animals or plants comprising nucleic acid molecules of the present invention.

Claims

1. An isolated human monoclonal antibody, or antigen-binding portion thereof, that specifically binds SARS-CoV S protein, comprising light chain variable (VL) and heavy chain variable (VH) domains that are at least 99% identical in amino acid sequence to the VL domain shown as SEQ ID NO:60 and the VH domain shown as SEQ ID NO:58, respectively, of the monoclonal antibody 3C7.
2. An isolated human monoclonal antibody, or antigen-binding portion thereof, that specifically binds SARS-CoV S protein, comprising:
 - (a) a heavy chain variable domain amino acid sequence that comprises the amino acid sequence of SEQ ID NO:58
 - (b) a light chain variable domain amino acid sequence that comprises the amino acid sequence of SEQ ID NO:60; or
 - (c) a heavy chain variable domain of (a) and a light chain variable domain of (b).
3. An isolated monoclonal antibody, or antigen-binding portion thereof, that specifically binds human SARS-CoV S protein, comprising:
 - (a) a heavy chain variable domain that comprises the amino acid sequences of the heavy chain CDR1, CDR2 and CDR3 of the antibody 3C7 shown in SEQ ID NO:58; and
 - (b) a light chain variable domain that comprises the amino acid sequences of the light chain CDR1, CDR2 and CDR3 of the antibody 3C7 shown in SEQ ID NO:60.
4. An isolated monoclonal

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Owners (US)
 Amgen Inc
Executed: Dec 14, 2008

Inventors
Babcock John S , Prabhakar Bellur S , Coughlin Melissa

US Classifications
530/387.3 530/388.8 530/388.3

Applicants
Amgen Inc

IPC Classifications

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Since new inventions will not be available to the public until at least 18 months from December 2019 as this waiting period is still in effect and provisional patenting is a standard, we created a Lens query for scientific publications relevant to the spike protein and SARS-CoV-2 that we can keep updated to provide the latest advances in our understanding of this region and how it the work is translated into treatment options. [Scholarly works collection relevant to Spike gene/protein](#) is available in Lens.org

and further analysis on the conducted research work over time, key authors/institutions involved, and aggregated works per field of study can now be visualized and available to the public.

Top Author Display Name over time

[View as Lens result](#)

Field of Study Grouped Bar Chart

[View as Lens result](#)

Top Funding by Document Count

* represents grouped institutes [View as Lens result](#)

Recently relevant works

- Distinct Structural Flexibility within SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein Reveals Potential Therapeutic Targets**

Serena H Chen ¹, M Todd Young ², John Gounley ¹, Christopher B Stanley ¹, Debandhu Bhowmik ²

bioRxiv, Apr 18, 2020

0 Patent Citations Reference Count: 33

Preprint 10.1101/2020.04.17.047548 3018998206
- Sex-Specific SARS-CoV-2 Mortality: Among Hormone-Modulated ACE2 Expression, Risk of Venous Thromboembolism and Hypovitaminosis D.**

Sandro La Vignera ¹, Rossella Cennerella ¹, Rosita A Condorelli ¹, Francesco Torre ¹, Antonio Aversa ², Aldo E Calogero ¹

International Journal of Molecular Sciences, Issue: 6, Volume: 21, Pages: 2948. Apr 22, 2020

0 Patent Citations 16 Scholarly Citations Reference Count: 31

Journal Article 10.3390/ijms21062948 32351343 3017817496
- COVID-19: Immunology and treatment options.**

Susanne Felsenstein ¹, Jenny A Herbert ², Paul S McNamara ², Christian M Hedrich ²

Clinical Immunology, Volume: 215, Pages: 106448-106448. Apr 27, 2020

0 Patent Citations 34 Scholarly Citations Reference Count: 205

Journal Article 10.1016/j.clim.2020.106448 32353634 7185015 3018494531
- ACE2 polymorphisms and individual susceptibility to SARS-CoV-2 infection: insights from an in silico study**

Matteo Calzavara ¹, Patricia Forgez ², Antonio Iannelli ^{3,4}, Cecilia Buccì ¹, Marco Alifano ², Pietro Alifano ⁴

bioRxiv, Apr 24, 2020

0 Patent Citations 2 Scholarly Citations Reference Count: 89

Preprint 10.1101/2020.04.23.057042 3019292816
- Saliva Glycoproteins Bind to Spike Protein of SARS-CoV-2**

Dapeng Zhou, Chenghao Wu

May 11, 2020

0 Patent Citations Reference Count: 0

Preprint 10.20944/preprints202005.0192.v1 3021255851

[View as Lens result](#)

Spike-host Interactions

How does SARS-CoV-2 interact with its host to cause COVID-19?

As with SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2 co-opts the soluble ectodomain of the human peptidase angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), predominantly but not exclusively, for cell entry ([Hoffman et al., 2020](#)). The Spike glycoprotein trimer initiates infection by 1) binding to ACE2 using its N-Terminal domain and 2) fusing the viral lipid envelope with cellular membranes via its C-Terminal domain. To trigger the fusion machinery, the spike protein needs to be cleaved at two sites, S1/S2 and S2'. Cleavage at S1/S2 was shown to be mediated by the proprotein convertase furin, a type I transmembrane protein that is ubiquitously expressed in eukaryotic tissues and cells and cleaves at polybasic motifs of R-X-R/K-R↓. Cleavage at S2' is mediated by protease serine 2 (TMPRSS2) that cleaves at single arginine or lysine residues (R/K↓), a monobasic cleavage site ([Hoffman et al., 2020](#), [Walls et al., 2020](#)). Use of either TMPRSS2 or furin inhibitors or both together renders the spike protein fusion inactive and therefore prevents virus entry ([Bestle et al., 2020](#)). Cleavage sites are absent from SARS-CoV-1 and their presence in SARS-CoV-2 is most likely an acquisition by [recombination from bats](#).

The N-terminal extracellular domain of ACE2 possesses 6 canonical sequons for N-linked glycosylation and several potential O-linked sites whereas the spike glycoprotein trimer contain 66 canonical sequons for N-linked glycosylation and a number of potential O-linked glycosylation sites ([Zhao et al., 2020](#)), [[Watanabe et al., 2020](#)](10.1126/science.abb9983)). Predicting studies have identified potential ACE2 glycan-S glycan interaction sites, however, they have also revealed that microheterogeneity is evident at most glycosylation sites of both S and ACE2. Each site can be modified with one of several glycan structures, generating site-specific glycosylation portfolios. Considering that in humans, glycosylation states vary based on age, underlying disease and ethnicity, [Zhao et al., 2020](#) suggested that glycosylation portfolios may partially explain the variation in individual susceptibility to infection. Analyses of the Spike trimer extracted from infectious SARS-CoV-2 virions harvested from airway cells or patients should reveal a more accurate glycosylation pattern in that interaction. The role of O-linked glycans that flank the cleavage sites has also recently been attributed to masking polypeptide epitopes and directly modulating Spike protein-ACE2 interactions ([Zhao et al., 2020](#)).

Another important recent finding has been the discovery that ACE2 is a human interferon-stimulated gene ([Zeigler et al., 2020](#)). Thus, a careful examination and investigation of ACE2/S glycan site profiles under various levels of interferons in the human epithelial cells may uncover how such host factors protect or weaken the defense system during virus entry.

Studies looking at viral infection of human lung cells showed that shortly after binding ACE2, the proteolytic activation of spike at the cleavage site (RRAR) at the S1/S2 spike junction occurs and is followed by another activation by TMPRSS2 ([Hoffman et al., 2020](#)). And the 2.5-Å crystal structure of the C-Terminal domain of SARS-CoV-2 in complex with ACE2 revealed a higher affinity for receptor

binding in SARS-CoV-2 than in SARS-CoV-1. Monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) as well as murine polyclonal antisera against SARS-S1/receptor binding domain were unable to bind to the SARS-CoV-2 S protein, confirming that there are differences in antigenicity between these two viruses ([Wang et al., 2020](#)).

Unlike SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2 seems more contagious and exhibits varied clinical symptoms in its hosts. When SARS-CoV-2 infection is associated with respiratory-like symptoms, studies showed that the virus enters the respiratory tract via the ciliated nasal epithelial cells where increased ACE2 and TMPRSS2 expression was detected and infection seems to proceed from the upper to the lower respiratory tract epithelial cells. Researchers have identified the mucus-producing goblet secretory cells where ACE 2 is highly expressed but also found that ACE2 can be expressed in type II pneumocytes in the lung and absorptive enterocytes within the gut ([Zeigler et al., 2020](#)). Because ACE2 co-expression with TMPRSS2 in respiratory tissues is consistently observed in such a rare subset of epithelial cells, researchers do not know yet whether both enzymes are needed on the same cell to activate cell entry or soluble proteases can mediate SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein activation to invade ACE2 single-positive cells (reviewed in [Zeigler et al., 2020](#)). The authors predict that the timing and cellular location of Spike protein activation are critical for virus entry.

Virus infection can also be associated with headache, nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea, recognized in about 10% of the COVID-19 patients ([D'Amico et al., 2020](#)). Whether these symptoms are correlated with severe infectivity or mortality still require further studies, but it is a common feature, based on other coronavirus infections, to have intestinal involvement and diarrhea associated with respiratory symptoms. For a more general review on virus infection, please see [Matheson, N.J and Lehner, P.J., 2020](#).

In some cases, virus infection was found to be associated with asymptomatic individuals who appear to harbor comparable viral loads and are capable of spreading the virus ([Rothe et al., 2020](#)) yet possibly recover with minimal treatment. From a public health preparedness perspective, such findings are alarming as the cases are hard to identify and virus spread is difficult to track. Considering these uncertainties, health care officials are using incoming research or clinical studies to build various mitigation scenarios. Here are the Planned pandemic scenarios developed by the [US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention](#).

For those who would like to explore related works on SARS-CoV-2-host entry process, we have assembled a dynamic public Lens scholarly collection, SARS-CoV-2: Cell entry that can be accessed from the Data sources tab.

Efforts to better understand virus entry are complemented with research on the various stages of the virus infection cycle. In particular, the crucial role of the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (nsp12) in RNA replication in the cytoplasm and 3'-5' ribonuclease (nsp14) that mediates the proofreading

mechanism upon the synthesis of subgenomic mRNAs. From a public health perspective though and to mitigate virus spread, several studies have investigated virus transmission routes.

With incubation times of 2-14 days and increased spread of SARS-CoV-2, the following virus transmission routes have been contemplated in humans: a) respiratory transmission via contact with liquid droplets by COVID-19 infected patients ([Anfinrud et al., 2020](#)), b) close contact with infected individuals including through saliva (<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-IPC-2020.4>), c) contact with surfaces and material that are virus- contaminated ([van Doremalen et al., 2020](#)), d) possible airborne transmission via aerosols in closed indoor settings with poor ventilation or leaked toilet pipes ([Tang et al., 2020](#)), or e) vertical transmission from an infected mother to her newborn ([Juan et al., 2020](#)) fecal-oral transmission ([Xiao et al., 2020](#)). The lack of standardized protocols to research some of these routes, the number of patient cases needed to prove transmission, and the lack of available resources to conduct such experiments over time makes it hard to conclude from the reviewed literature. So, until further evidence is available to confirm and/or refute the ad hoc findings of some routes of transmission, no conclusion can be drawn yet. To track new studies on the virus transmission topic in the Lens, you can either follow this dynamic and public collection, [SARS-CoV-2: Transmission](#) or clone to edit or refine the saved query and then set the alert notification in your own private and secure work area.

[David Cyranoski, 2020](#)

Virus Spread and Diagnostics

Considering the current state of COVID 19 crisis, quick and reliable detection of the disease and expanded testing capabilities are still lacking. Challenging issues range from the fact that people can be infectious with and without symptoms and thus hard to test and contact trace. Diagnostic resources needed for proper testing of every citizen regardless of symptoms are scarce in many countries, standardized best practices to perform, assess and verify highly sensitive and specific tests are hard to implement, and timely test results before the tested person is able to infect other people are limited. Moreover, only a few of the emerging in vitro diagnostic assays are proven to be robust enough to deal with the pandemic. A high percent of false negative results and cross reactivity with other associated diseases are among the most drawbacks reported for such tests and therefore, to better understand the dynamics of virus spread in a population and perform accurate diagnosis of COVID-19 individuals, additional screening methodologies, monitoring of viral genes variations, and a careful assessment and interpretation of the current diagnostic tools are needed.

What, when, where and how to test?

Testing for the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in humans is mainly through the use of in vitro diagnostic assays. These include primarily molecular amplification and detection of viral genomic RNA, serological testing of viral proteins, and detection of antibodies. Serial testing with additional medical tests based on the patient clinical history are also performed to complement or confirm initial tests.

The structure of SARS-CoV-2 allows for the broad use of the surface glycoprotein Spike, Envelope, Membrane, and Nucleocapsid proteins in diagnostic tests as these are expressed at various concentration levels during COVID-19 infection cycle and can be tracked in some cases. The S1 subunit of the spike protein is the most variable immunogenic antigen and used for neutralizing antibodies whereas the nucleocapsid protein is highly immunogenic and can be detected in both serum and urine samples around 10 days post infection ([Paules et al., 2020](#)).

The COVID testing landscape varies across different countries. In China, Korea, New Zealand and to some extent Australia and Canada, testing is combined with contact tracing to limit the number of infections and decrease virus spread in the country. In the USA, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) [guidelines](#) recommend that testing be associated with licensed healthcare providers and performed in labs (public, commercial, or clinical). To accelerate testing, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration began to grant an Emergency Use Authorization (EUA) on diagnostic assays produced by various entities. The decision about who should be tested is left open and based on the discretion of state, local health departments and/or healthcare providers.

For early screening of individuals with fever and respiratory symptoms, viral RNA amplification from swabs in the upper respiratory tract is used along with stool and urine samples, when additional symptoms such as diarrhea or gastrointestinal pain are manifested ([Holshue et al., 2020](#)). Swab-based SARS-CoV-2 testing encompasses primarily swabs from nasopharyngeal (NP), oropharyngeal (OP), and sputum swabs. Saliva sampling is also being considered as a reliable non invasive alternative method for antibody detection of SARS-CoV-2 infected individuals and in population (check Rutgers University issued EUA in the molecular tests list next tab and [Randad et al., 2020](#) or [Kai-Wang To et al., 2020](#)). In some cases, blood-based samples or samples from the lower respiratory tract are also allowed.

Stool sampling or rectal swab-testing was suggested to monitor the effectiveness of virus treatment and determine appropriate termination date of quarantine based on persistent viral shedding from the digestive system of pediatric SARS-CoV-2 infection cases and the assumption that this process might be greater and last longer than that from the respiratory tract ([Xu et al, 2020](#)). Evidence for the use of rectal swabs [has been accumulating](#) also for the diagnosis of gastrointestinal infections ([Xiao et al., 2020](#)) and demonstrate fecal-oral transmission, in particular, when the presence of an infectious viral RNA was recently proven from stool samples ([Xiao et al., 2020](#)).

Figure 2. Detection probability of viral RNA or antibody (IgA, IgM, and IgG) against SARS-CoV-2 during the course of infection (relative to symptom onset). The testing windows of nucleic acid amplification tests (RT-PCR, blue) and serology tests (antibody, green) are indicated. Ig = immunoglobulin; RT-PCR = real-time reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction; SARS-CoV-2 = severe acute respiratory syndrome-coronavirus 2. [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com].

[Chau et al., 2020](#). Also, this recent report has a more detailed description on diagnostic assays that are in use or *in development*

Table 2. Comparison of In Vitro SARS-CoV-2 Tests Granted Emergency Use Authorizations by the US FDA

	Molecular	Antigen	Serology
Test type	Viral	Viral	Antibody
Diagnostic test	Yes	Yes	No
Description	Nucleic acid amplification test to detect viral RNA	Detects viral proteins in the nasal cavity	Detects the presence of IgA, IgM & IgG antibodies against SARS-CoV-2
Measure	Current infection with SARS-CoV-2	Current infection with SARS-CoV-2	Past exposure to SARS-CoV-2
Platform technology	RT-PCR, LAMP, CRISPR	Lateral flow	Lateral flow, ELISA, CIA
Sample type	Nasal or throat swab, saliva, bronchoalveolar lavage fluid	Nasal or throat swab	Blood draw (plasma, serum, whole blood) or finger stick
Testing window	Days 1–28 after symptom onset, optimal days 3–12	Days 1–28 after symptom onset, optimal days 3–12	IgA/IgM: from day 5 after symptom onset, optimal days 14–21; IgG: from day 14 after symptom onset up to 6 weeks
Result turnaround time	Same day or up to a week (depending on location); point-of-care option available (within 1–2 hours)	Rapid, point-of-care (within 15 minutes)	Same day or up to 1–3 days (depending on location); point-of-care option available (within 15–30 minutes)

CIA = chemiluminescent immunoassay; CRISPR = clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats; ELISA = enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; FDA = US Food and Drug Administration; Ig = immunoglobulin; LAMP = loop-mediated isothermal amplification; RT-PCR = real-time reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction; SARS-CoV-2 = severe acute respiratory syndrome-coronavirus 2.

[Chau et al., 2020](#)

Randad et al., 2020. Figure 6 (Top part). Comparison of saliva and serum SARS-CoV-2 antigen-specific IgG (red), IgA (blue), and IgM (green) responses vs. days post-COVID-19 symptom onset. The trajectories of IgG (red), IgA (blue), and IgM (green) responses are estimated using a LOESS curve. Dashed lines indicate cut off values for IgG (red), IgA (blue), and IgM (green). Note. Sino Biol.: Sino Biological; N: nucleocapsid protein; ECD: S1: S1 subunit

of spike protein; S2: S2 subunit of spike protein; ectodomain (S1 subunit+S2 subunit of the spike protein); RBD: receptor binding domain; (h): produced in human cell; MFI=mean fluorescence intensity.

Emergency approved diagnostics

Molecular tests based on nucleic acid amplification of SARS-CoV-2 genes

Issued emergency use authorizations (EUAs) for the various COVID-19 diagnostic tests available in the USA are reviewed periodically to either extend or revoke permission based on their accuracy, performance, and usefulness. As of August 21, 2020, there were 184 approved EUAs (commercial and laboratory-developed tests) which include 145 molecular tests, 39 serological tests, and 4 antigen tests (See list below). For some quick introduction on the individual diagnostic assays, their performance and drawbacks, and the applied processes, Lens recommends these few studies in the public collection [SARS-CoV-2: Diagnostic assays-Broad](#) to start with. The highlight is that the current polymerase chain reaction-based or deep sequencing methods of SARS-CoV-2 diagnosis rely on an actively replicating virus in enough quantities to be detected. While these are useful, they are not robust enough to use independently of other tests. They fail when viral load is still weak or suppressed by an immune response or when there is an error in sampling. However, when molecular tests are used in conjunction with serological tests, the sensitivity of detection of the virus increases, especially in infected patients and may lead to more effective and reliable contact tracing results [Espejo et al., 2020](#).

Data source: FDA, Emergency Use Authorization

Abbreviations used in the Tables: Technology column: CLIA = chemiluminescence immunoassay; ELISA = enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; ECLIA = electrochemiluminescence immunoassay; FMIA = fluorescent microsphere Immunoassay, CMIA = chemiluminescent microparticle immunoassay.

Authorized Settings are: H - Laboratories certified under the Clinical Laboratory Improvement Amendments of 1988 (CLIA), 42 U.S.C. §263a, that meet requirements to perform high complexity tests. M - Laboratories certified under the Clinical Laboratory Improvement Amendments of 1988 (CLIA), 42 U.S.C. §263a, that meet requirements to perform moderate complexity tests. W - Patient care settings operating under a CLIA Certificate of Waiver.

For live links on the tables below, please visit the live version of this report at <https://link.lens.org/f0cT80MarSd>

Molecular amplification of viral genomic RNA assays are usually used during the active stage of SARS-CoV-2

Diagnostic (most recent letter of Authorization)	Entity	Date EUA First Issued	Authorized Setting(s)
COVID-19 Nucleic Acid RT-PCR Test Kit	ZhuHai Sinochips Bioscience Co., Ltd.	17/08/2020	H
SalivaDirect	Yale School of Public Health, Department of Epidemiology of Microbial Diseases	15/08/2020	H
Pro-AmpRT SARS-CoV-2 Test	Pro-Lab Diagnostics	13/08/2020	H
Biomeme SARS-CoV-2 Real-Time RT-PCR Test	Biomeme, Inc.	11/08/2020	H
LumiraDx SARS-CoV-2 RNA STAR	LumiraDx UK Ltd.	11/08/2020	H
Alpha Genomix TaqPath SARS-CoV-2 Combo Assay	Alpha Genomix Laboratories	10/08/2020	H
Solaris Multiplex SARS-CoV-2 Assay	Solaris Diagnostics	10/08/2020	H
GWU SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR Test	George Washington University Public Health Laboratory	7/08/2020	H
Helix COVID-19 NGS Test	Helix OpCo LLC (dba Helix)	6/08/2020	H
ViroKey SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR Test	Vela Operations Singapore Pte Ltd	5/08/2020	H
Cleveland Clinic SARS-CoV-2 Assay	Cleveland Clinic Robert J. Tomsich Pathology and Laboratory Medicine Institute	3/08/2020	H
Genus SARS-CoV-2 Assay	ISPM Labs, LLC dba Capstone Healthcare	3/08/2020	H
Wren Laboratories COVID-19 PCR Test	Wren Laboratories LLC	3/08/2020	H
SARS-CoV-2 Test Kit	Xiamen Zeesan Biotech Co., Ltd.	31/07/2020	H
Lilly SARS-CoV-2 Assay	Eli Lilly and Company	27/07/2020	H
SNL-NM 2019 nCoV Real-Time RT-PCR Diagnostic Assay	Sandia National Laboratories	27/07/2020	H
Novel Coronavirus Fast Nucleic Acid Detection Kit	Jiangsu CoWin Biotech Co., Ltd.	24/07/2020	H
Helix COVID-19 Test	Helix OpCo LLC (dba Helix)	23/07/2020	H
QuantiVirus SARS-CoV-2 Multiplex Test Kit	DiaCarta, Inc.	21/07/2020	H
QraRisk COVID-19 RT-PCR	Access Genetics, LLC	17/07/2020	H
Boston Heart COVID-19 RT-PCR Test	Boston Heart Diagnostics	16/07/2020	H
PowerChek 2019-nCoV Real-time PCR Kit	KogeneBiotech Co., Ltd.	13/07/2020	H
PhoenixDx SARS-CoV-2 Multiplex	Trax Management Services Inc.	13/07/2020	H

Molecular, Home Collection

Diagnostic (most recent letter of Authorization)	Entity	Date EUA First Issued	Authorized Setting(s)
Ethos Laboratories SARS-CoV-2 MALDI-TOF Assay	Ethos Laboratories	3/08/2020	H
CRL Rapid Response	Clinical Reference Laboratory, Inc.	30/07/2020	H
Quest Diagnostics HA SARS-CoV-2 Assay	Quest Diagnostics Infectious Disease, Inc.	15/07/2020	H
Quest Diagnostics RC SARS-CoV-2 Assay	Quest Diagnostics Infectious Disease, Inc.	15/07/2020	H
Quest Diagnostics PF SARS-CoV-2 Assay	Quest Diagnostics Infectious Disease, Inc.	15/07/2020	H
Compass Laboratory Services SARS-CoV2 Assay	Compass Laboratory Services, LLC	13/07/2020	H
KPMAS COVID-19 Test	Kaiser Permanente Mid-Atlantic States	13/06/2020	H
Phosphorus COVID-19 RT-qPCR Test	Phosphorus Diagnostics LLC	4/06/2020	H
Gravity Diagnostics COVID-19 Assay	Gravity Diagnostics, LLC	1/06/2020	H
LetsGetChecked Coronavirus Test	PrivaPath Diagnostics, Inc.	28/05/2020	H
SARS-CoV-2 Test	Exact Sciences Laboratories	22/05/2020	H
P23 Labs TaqPath SARS-CoV-2 Assay	P23 Labs, LLC.	21/05/2020	H
Color SARS Cov-2 Diagnostic Assay	Color Genomics, Inc.	18/05/2020	H
Assurance SARS-CoV-2 Panel	Assurance Scientific Laboratories	15/05/2020	H
Fulgent COVID-19 by RT-PCR Test	Fulgent Therapeutics, LLC	15/05/2020	H
Rutgers Clinical Genomics Laboratory TaqPath SARS-CoV-2 Assay	Rutgers Clinical Genomics Laboratory at RUCDR Infinite Biologics - Rutgers University	10/04/2020	H
Everlywell COVID-19 Test Home Collection Kit	Everlywell, Inc.	15/05/2020	N/A

A scaled up molecular assay based on sample pooling (Multiplex RT-PCR)

Technology	Diagnostic (most recent letter of Authorization)	Entity	Date EUA First Issued	Authorized Setting(s)
Molecular, Home Collection, Sample Pooling	Quest SARS-CoV-2 rRT-PCR	Quest Diagnostics Infectious Disease, Inc.	17/03/2020	H
Molecular, Home Collection, Sample Pooling, Screening	COVID-19 RT-PCR Test	Laboratory Corporation of America	16/03/2020	H
Molecular, Multi-analyte	Influenza SARS-CoV-2 Multiplex Assay	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)	2/07/2020	H
Molecular, Multi-analyte	BioFire Respiratory Panel 2.1	BioFire Diagnostics, LLC	1/05/2020	H, M
Molecular, Multi-analyte	QIAstat-Dx Respiratory SARS-CoV-2 Panel	QIAGEN GmbH	30/03/2020	H, M
Molecular, Sample Pooling	Poplar SARS-CoV-2 TMA Pooling assay	Poplar Healthcare	3/08/2020	H
Molecular, Sample Pooling	UCSD RC SARS-CoV-2 Assay	University of California San Diego Health	31/07/2020	H

Serological Assays

These tests detect antibodies that are important parts of the human mucosal and systemic immune response with demonstrated ability to protect against most viral pathogens. Apart from virus neutralization, antibodies have the capacity to induce antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity, antibody-dependent cellular phagocytosis, or antibody-dependent complement activation. As a result of SARS-CoV-2 infection, these assays were deployed to profile each or all of these antibodies (IgA, IgG, and IgM) produced in patients at various stages of infection. Research so far shows that Lateral Flow immunoassays are not suitable for use with patients and instead the Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assays (ELISA) can be adjusted to detect all these antibodies at the various stages of the infection.

Serology, IgG, IGM

Technology	Diagnostic (most recent letter of Authorization)	Entity	Date EUA First Issued	Authorized Setting(s)
Serology IgG, CLIA	Diazyme DZ-Lite SARS-CoV-2 IgG CLIA Kit	Diazyme Laboratories, Inc.	8/07/2020	H, M
Serology IgG, CLIA	Access SARS-CoV-2 IgG	Beckman Coulter, Inc.	26/06/2020	H, M
Serology IgG, CLIA	Babson Diagnostics eC19G1	Babson Diagnostics, Inc.	23/06/2020	H
Serology IgG, CLIA	LIAISON SARS-CoV-2 S1/S2 IgG	DiaSorin Inc.	24/04/2020	H, M
Serology IgG, CLIA	VITROS Immunodiagnostic Products Anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG Reagent Pack	Ortho-Clinical Diagnostics, Inc.	24/04/2020	H, M
Serology IgG, CMIA	SARS-CoV-2 IgG assay	Abbott Laboratories Inc.	26/04/2020	H, M
Serology IgG, ELFA	VIDAS SARS-CoV-2 IgG	bioMérieux SA	6/08/2020	H, M
Serology IgG, ELISA	SARS-CoV-2 RBD IgG test	Emory Medical Laboratories	15/06/2020	H
Serology IgG, ELISA	SCoV-2 Detect IgG ELISA	InBios International, Inc.	10/06/2020	H
Serology IgG, ELISA	Anti-SARS-CoV-2 ELISA	EUROIMMUN US Inc.	4/05/2020	H
Serology IgG, ELISA	COVID-19 ELISA IgG Antibody Test	Mount Sinai Laboratory	15/04/2020	H
Serology IgG, FMIA	xMAP SARS-CoV-2 Multi-Antigen IgG Assay	Luminex Corporation	16/07/2020	H
Serology IgG, Semi-quantitative	Atellica IM SARS-CoV-2 IgG	Siemens Healthcare Diagnostics Inc.	31/07/2020	H, M
Serology IgG, Semi-quantitative	ADVIA Centaur SARS-CoV-2 IgG	Siemens Healthcare Diagnostics Inc.	31/07/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG Lateral Flow	LYHER Novel Coronavirus IgM/IgG Antibody Combo Test Kit	Hangzhou Laihe Biotech Co., Ltd.	19/06/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG Lateral Flow	Biohit SARS-CoV-2 IgM/IgG Antibody Test Kit	Biohit Healthcare (Hefei) Co. Ltd.	18/06/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, CLIA	Vibrant COVID-19 Ab Assay	Vibrant America Clinical Labs	4/06/2020	H
Serology IgM and IgG, CLIA	BioCheck SARS-CoV-2 IgG and IgM Combo Test	BioCheck, Inc.	17/08/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, Lateral Flow	CareStart COVID-19 IgM/IgG	Access Bio, Inc.	24/07/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, Lateral Flow	BIOTIME SARS-CoV-2 IgG/IgM Rapid Qualitative Test	Xiamen Biotime Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	24/07/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, Lateral Flow	Rapid COVID-19 IgM/IgG Combo Test Kit	Megna Health, Inc.	17/07/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, Lateral Flow	Sienna-Clarity COVIBLOCK COVID-19 IgG/IgM Rapid Test Cassette	Salofa Oy	13/07/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, Lateral Flow	Assure COVID-19 IgG/IgM Rapid Test Device	Assure Tech. (Hangzhou Co., Ltd)	6/07/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, Lateral Flow	RightSign COVID-19 IgG/IgM Rapid Test Cassette	Hangzhou Biotest Biotech Co., Ltd.	4/06/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, Lateral Flow	COVID-19 IgG/IgM Rapid Test Cassette	Healgen Scientific LLC	29/05/2020	H, M
Serology IgM and IgG, Lateral Flow	qSARS-CoV-2 IgG/IgM Rapid Test	Cellex Inc.	1/04/2020	H, M
Serology IgM, CLIA	Diazyme DZ-Lite SARS-CoV-2 IgM CLIA Kit	Diazyme Laboratories, Inc.	17/08/2020	H, M
Serology IgM, ELFA	VIDAS SARS-CoV-2 IgM	bioMérieux SA	6/08/2020	H, M
Serology IgM, ELISA	SCoV-2 Detect IgM ELISA	InBios International, Inc.	30/06/2020	H

Serology Total Antibodies

Technology	Diagnostic (most recent letter of Authorization)	Entity	Date EUA First Issued	Authorized Setting(s)
Serology Total Antibody, CLIA	VITROS Immunodiagnostic Products Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Total Reagent Pack	Ortho Clinical Diagnostics, Inc.	14/04/2020	H, M
Serology Total Antibody, CLIA	Dimension EXL SARS-CoV-2 Total antibody assay	Siemens Healthcare Diagnostics Inc.	8/06/2020	H, M
Serology Total Antibody, CLIA	Dimension Vista SARS-CoV-2 Total antibody assay	Siemens Healthcare Diagnostics Inc.	8/06/2020	H, M
Serology Total Antibody, CLIA	ADVIA Centaur SARS-CoV-2 Total	Siemens Healthcare Diagnostics Inc.	29/05/2020	H, M
Serology Total Antibody, CLIA	Atellica IM SARS-CoV-2 Total	Siemens Healthcare Diagnostics Inc.	29/05/2020	H, M
Serology Total Antibody, ECLIA	Elecsys Anti-SARS-CoV-2	Roche Diagnostics	2/05/2020	H, M
Serology Total Antibody, ELISA	WANTAI SARS-CoV-2 Ab ELISA	Beijing Wantai Biological Pharmacy Enterprise Co., Ltd.	5/08/2020	H
Serology Total Antibody, ELISA	Platelia SARS-CoV-2 Total Ab assay	Bio-Rad Laboratories	29/04/2020	H
Serology Total Antibody, FMIA	New York SARS-CoV Microsphere Immunoassay for Antibody Detection	Wadsworth Center, New York State Department of Health	30/04/2020	H
Serology Total Antibody, Lateral Flow	WANTAI SARS-CoV-2 Ab Rapid Test	Beijing Wantai Biological Pharmacy Enterprise Co., Ltd.	10/07/2020	H, M

Antigen and Immunoassay mainly for the rapid detection of viral or host specific proteins

Technology	Diagnostic (most recent letter of Authorization)	Entity	Date EUA First Issued	Authorized Setting(s)
Antigen	LumiraDx SARS-CoV-2 Ag Test	LumiraDx UK Ltd.	18/08/2020	H, M, W
Antigen	BD Veritor System for Rapid Detection of SARS-CoV-2	Becton, Dickinson and Company (BD)	2/07/2020	H, M, W
Antigen	Sofia 2 SARS Antigen FIA	Quidel Corporation	8/05/2020	H, M, W
Immunoassay-IL-6	Elecsys IL-6	Roche Diagnostics	2/06/2020	H, M

Mucosal and systemic immunity

Will our immune system resist SARS-CoV-2?

In the previous sections, we reviewed studies showing the presence of SARS-CoV-2 mutant clouds at different locations around the world. We also briefly described the virus co-opting of the host cell machinery to enter the respiratory tract of the human body using its spike protein that binds to the human cell receptor ACE2 and proteolytically get cleaved by host proteases ahead of its fusion with the cell membrane. Considering its unique capabilities and ease of spread across various cultures, age groups, and human health pre-dispositions, SARS-CoV-2 seems to exhibit a more personalized clinical manifestation in the infected host based on a specific and nuanced interaction with that host immune system.

Clinical studies from the past few months indicate that SARS-CoV-2 infection extends beyond the initial COVID-19 described symptoms and some suggest that the disease may even be a consequence of two rather than one syndrome. After a serious pneumonia-like symptoms post the initial incubation period, "some patients suffer from a serious local and systemic immune response, e.g. a form of sepsis" and doctors have difficulties managing disease progression which seems to be associated with the patient's immune system and often results in death ([Jacobs, 2020](#)). The presence

of a wide spectrum of clinical symptoms associated with SARS-CoV-2 ranges from individuals harboring the virus but not exhibiting any symptoms to those who became severely affected with pneumonia-like symptoms, to those individuals who exhibit very aggravated symptoms leading to fatal lung failure or other complications. Immunological studies have also shown individualized and unique kinetics of humoral responses suggesting that the interplay between the virus and the host immune system is an area that merits a careful examination.

As with SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2 with COVID-19-like symptoms induces a mucosal and systemic immune response ([Cervia et al., 2020](#)). However, with mild to moderate symptoms, only mucosal antibody IgA response is detected without a systemic antibody production. But, if disease severity is moderate, a delayed systemic response can be observed. With very severe symptoms, including severe ARDS, very high IgA and IgG systemic antibody production was observed.

These results agree with earlier research works on SARS-CoV-1 that show that the mucosal immune response and the relevant cell types are important determinants of the clinical symptoms and severity of COVID-19 disease ([Paces et al., 2020](#)). These authors extrapolated that “self” vs. “non-self” discrimination is mainly mediated via recognition of the viral nucleic acids as pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) by specific pathogen recognition receptors (PRRs) in the cytosol". SARS-CoV-2 is predicted to encode some proteins that interfere with PRR-mediated viral sensing and subsequent effector viral-controlling mechanisms, for example, blocking Interferon responses or viral RNA recognition.

Based on the current evidence, SARS-CoV-2 enters the human body via ciliated nasal epithelial cells, and according to [Strugnell and Wijburg, 2010](#), mucosal IgA production will be activated to act as the first line of defense. Protection can result from blocking any contact between the virus and the mucosal epithelial cell surface (a process known as ‘immune exclusion’) and neutralizing viral replication in those cells (known as ‘intracellular neutralization’). Several studies have now shown that in the majority of COVID-19 infected patients, a specific IgA response can in fact be detected within the first week of infection ([Padoan et al. 2020](#)), and the public [collection on IgA](#).

Mucosal IgA is mostly produced in a dimeric form linked by a protein called joining chain. Its expression is mediated and regulated by a polymeric Ig receptor (pIgR), a glycosylated transmembrane protein consisting of five Ig domains forming the pIgR ectodomain also referred to as secretory component (SC), a short transmembrane domain, and an intracellular domain. The secretory component is covalently bound to the antibody portion and constitutes an integral part of the Secretory IgA complex. The heavily N-glycosylated SC part of SIgA protects the complex from proteolysis ([Pabst & Slack, 2019](#)).

Upon infection, infected epithelial cells produce interferons and then pro-inflammatory cytokines, including interleukin-6. T cells are activated mainly to reduce the viral load and more specific antibodies are released to provide systemic immune responses. But, if the inflammatory immune

response gets overactivated, it can lead to a dysfunctional inflammatory state (cytokine storm) and subsequent immune exhaustion, a phenomenon observed in some COVID-19 patients ([Shi et al., 2020](#)).

Cellular and humoral immunity

Upon B and T cell activation, specific antibodies (immunoglobulin M (IgM), immunoglobulin A (IgA), and immunoglobulin G (IgG)) are released. Production of IgM is short lived and leads to isotype switching to IgA and IgG, which persists for extended periods in the serum, nasal fluids and all secretions. While it is still not clear whether IgG confers protection against SARS-CoV-2 infection, studies on humoral responses to SARS-CoV-1 infection revealed that an increased level of IgG can aggravates the situation and leads to fatal acute lung injury if the inflammation-resolving response becomes dysfunctional. Liu et al., 2019 explained that:

"During acute infection, monocytes/macrophages often display a phenotype of classically activated macrophages. These cells mediate host defenses against viruses and also promote lung injury by producing nitric oxide (NO); ROS; IL-1, IL-6, and IL-8; and TNF. Simultaneously, some macrophages may become alternatively activated, exerting anti-inflammatory function and regulating wound healing by producing matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), growth factors, and anti-inflammatory cytokines, particularly TGF- β . When the pathogen or inflammatory stimulus is eliminated, proinflammatory macrophages diminish. The predominant macrophage population assumes a wound-healing phenotype. At the final recovery stage, macrophages show a regulatory/suppressive phenotype, secreting increased levels of IL-10, which facilitates the resolution of wound healing and restores homeostasis. When the wound-healing response is well organized and controlled, the inflammatory response resolves quickly, and normal tissue architecture is restored. Disturbances in wound-healing response can lead to uncontrolled production of inflammatory mediators, contributing to a state of persistent injury".

[Works on both SARS-CoV-1 and MERS-CoV](#) confirmed that anti-spike antibodies (anti-spike IgG) facilitate virus infection, provide the virus with an opportunity to modify its tropism, and extend its entry paths to new immune cells and circulate to infect other organ systems. Recently, [Jacobs, 2020](#) offered yet an alternative hypothesis to the commonly referred role of neutralizing antibodies. He argued that while anti-spike antibodies may protect against infection in epithelial cells (local immunity), their binding to the spike protein may potentiate virus infection of myeloid leukocytes. The author elaborated that "If myeloid leukocytes re-enter the circulation, they could spread the virus from a locoregional infection to a systemic disease. Disseminated

virus in combination with antibodies results in dispersed virus-antibody complexes that overstimulate the immune system".

In the case of COVID-19, increased levels of IgA and IgG at mucosal sites was observed and correlated with severe disease symptoms whereas in individuals with mild disease, systemic IgA and IgG was not detected. Further studies also showed that with increased disease severity, the serum levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines increased as well and this led to potential depletion and functional exhaustion of T cells (Zheng et al., 2020 and Paces et al., 2020). Hence the recommendation to pay attention to the early protective phase of the infection and boost immunity initially but then suppress it in the inflammatory immunity phase to minimize risks to lung inflammation (Shi et al., 2020).

Since each of the viral structural and non-structural proteins can elicit an immune response, recent efforts targeted epitope mapping of these proteins to identify potential human leukocyte antigen (HLA) binding peptides. Several candidates have now been identified from various viral genes exhibiting a robust viral antigenicity and immunogenicity. The prediction is that these may improve the immune responses of SARS-CoV-2 by eliciting adaptive immune responses by CD8+ cytotoxic T cell and CD4+ T helper cell and an innate immune response by Natural Killer (NK) cells (Marshan, 2020).

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the progression of COVID-19 infection and potential adjuvant interventions.

Shi et al., 2020

How long will SARS-CoV-2 immunity persist?

Based on SARS-CoV-1 research findings, antibody levels seem to drop within 2-3 years whereas the virus-specific memory T cells can be detected even 17 years after the initial infection (Le Bert et al., 2020). Mapping peptide epitopes in the SARS-CoV-2 Nucleocapsid protein (N), NSP7, and NSP13 in an effort to find those that trigger a specific T-cell response, the authors show that during the convalescent phase of COVID-19, infected individuals can develop specific CD4 and CD8 T cells primarily to the Nucleocapsid viral protein epitopes. These can be found in SARS-recovered and in unexposed individuals in various recognition patterns and ratios. Some of the N epitopes were previously also targeted by T cells as a result of SARS-CoV-1 infection.

These results imply that long-lasting T cell induction is possible in COVID-19 patients and when such cells are present due to earlier exposures by other related viruses or coronaviruses, it may protect against or affect the pathology of the invading new virus depending on infection stage.

Le Bert et al., 2020.

Fig. 4 | Immunodominance of SARS-CoV-2 responses in patients who recovered from COVID-19 and SARS, and in unexposed individuals. a, PBMCs of individuals who were not exposed to SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 (n = 37), recovered from SARS (n = 23) or COVID-19 (n = 36) were stimulated with peptide pools covering N (N-1, N-2), NSP7 and NSP13 (NSP13-1, NSP13-2, NSP13-3) of SARS-CoV-2 and analysed by ELISpot. The frequency of peptide-reactive cells is shown for each donor (dots or squares) and the bars represent the median frequency. Squares denote PBMC samples collected before July 2019. b, The percentage of individuals with N-specific, NSP7 and NSP13-specific responses, or N-, NSP7- and NSP13-specific responses in cohort. c, The composition of the SARS-CoV-2 response in

each responding unexposed donor (n = 19) is shown as a percentage of the total detected response. N-1, light blue; N-2, dark blue; NSP7, orange; NSP13-1, light red; NSP13-2, red; NSP13-3, dark red. d, Frequency of SARS-CoV-2-reactive cells in 11 unexposed donors to the indicated peptide pools directly ex vivo and after a 10-day expansion. e, A peptide pool matrix strategy was used for three individuals who were not exposed to SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2. The identified T cell epitopes were confirmed by ICS, and the sequences were aligned to the corresponding sequence of all coronaviruses known to infect humans.

Have these T cell epitope sequences been disclosed in patents?

If so, by whom and for what use? Could we identify more examples in the patent literature? Using PatSeq Finder in Lens.org, we conducted optimized similarity sequence searches on the three reported T Cell epitopes from Le Bert et al., 2020 publication. Results are embedded below showing similar sequences are disclosed in the claims and/or in the detailed description of granted patents and patent applications. To explore further the patents disclosing these sequences, we attach with each panel below a public Lens collection of [patents](#) disclosing sequences that are >80% similar and with >90% coverage.

<https://www.lens.org/lens/bio/patseqfinder#/results/9db97b2f-3cfc-41bb-a5e0-570f73ca598c>

View sequence search results in the Lens. Explore this public collection of [patents](#) disclosing similar sequences with >80% similarity and with >90% coverage.

<https://www.lens.org/lens/bio/patseqfinder#/results/8ae3502c-6294-4fd0-b006-f9b4dcee8475>

View results in the Lens. Explore the public collection of [patents](#) disclosing similar sequences with >90% similarity and with >90% coverage.

<https://www.lens.org/lens/bio/patseqfinder#/results/58f6cb90-73da-422b-8f6a-bde0f7f5ee33>

View sequence search results in the Lens. View the public collection of patents disclosing sequences that are >80% similar and with >90% coverage

Yu et al., 2020. FIGURE 1 Chronological profiles of antibodies in patients with coronavirus disease 2019. Samples collected since illness onset and during weeks 0–1, 1–2, 2–3, 3–4, 4–5, 5–6, 6–7 and 7–8 were pooled for analysis. a and b) The medians of the antibody detection values (luminescent values) of samples at the same time-point since onset in a) all patients and b) patients with severe illness. c–e) Time-serial changes of the levels of different antibodies in severe and nonsevere groups. The medians of antibody detection values (luminescent values) of samples at the same time-point since onset for c) IgA, d) IgG and e) IgM.

Vaccine Candidates

Being a cell-surface protein and crucial for cell entry and infectivity, the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 has been used in multiple vaccine types to elicit and generate neutralizing antibodies or to inhibit host-virus interactions.

On August 13, 2020, The World Health Organization (WHO) released a [draft landscape of COVID-19 vaccine candidates](#). The landscape lists 29 vaccine candidates in clinical evaluation and 138 others in a preclinical phase. All four vaccine types described earlier by [Callaway,2020](#) are now being evaluated; virus vaccines, viral vector vaccines, protein-based vaccines, and nucleic-acid vaccines.

Below, we use the referenced graphical representation for each virus vaccine type and list underneath it the WHO vaccine candidates with live links at <https://link.lens.org/f0cT80MarSd> to the clinical trials/interim report pages. The listed information was checked and edited for more transparency

about collaborations between various countries or between companies and vaccine brand names added where the information was available from press releases or companies websites.

Vaccine candidates in clinical evaluation

VIRUS VACCINES

At least seven teams are developing vaccines using the virus itself, in a weakened or inactivated form. Many existing vaccines are made in this way, such as those against measles and polio, but they require extensive safety testing. Sinovac Biotech in Beijing has started to test an inactivated version of SARS-CoV-2 in humans.

Weakened virus

A virus is conventionally weakened for a vaccine by being passed through animal or human cells until it picks up mutations that make it less able to cause disease. Codagenix in Farmingdale, New York, is working with the Serum Institute of India, a vaccine manufacturer in Pune, to weaken SARS-CoV-2 by altering its genetic code so that viral proteins are produced less efficiently.

Inactivated virus

In these vaccines, the virus is rendered uninfected using chemicals, such as formaldehyde, or heat. Making them, however, requires starting with large quantities of infectious virus.

[Callaway, 2020](#)

Inactivated Virus-Vaccines

COVID-19 Vaccine developer/manufacturer	Type of Candidate Vaccine	Clinical Stage			
		Phase 1	Phase 1/2	Phase 2	Phase 3
Sinovac Research and Development Co., Ltd. Or Sinovac Life Sciences Co., Ltd. /Butantan Institute (Brasil)/PT. Bio Farma (Indonesia)	Inactivated version of the virus (Corona Vac) referred to as Adsorbed COVID-19 (inactivated) Vaccine	-	NCT04383574 , NCT04352608 , Interim Report	-	NCT04456595 , 16202009080721WXFM0YX
Wuhan Institute of Biological Products(subsidiary)/Sinopharm (parental company)	Inactivated Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia (COVID-19) vaccine (Vero cells)	-	ChiCTR2000031809	-	ChiCTR2000034780
Beijing Institute of Biological Products(subsidiary)/Sinopharm (parental company)	Inactivated novel coronavirus (2019-CoV) vaccine (Vero cells)	-	ChiCTR2000032459	-	ChiCTR2000034780
Institute of Medical Biology, Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences and collaborators West China Second University Hospital, Yunnan Center for Disease Control and Prevention	Inactivated SARS-CoV-2 Vaccine	NCT04412538	NCT04470609	-	-
Bharat Biotech International Limited in collaboration with Indian Council of Medical Research	Whole Virion Inactivated SARS-CoV-2 Vaccine [BBV152]	-	NCT04471519	-	-

Data source: [draft landscape of COVID-19 vaccine candidates](#), press releases, and companies websites

Nucleic Acid-Based Vaccines

NUCLEIC-ACID VACCINES

At least 20 teams are aiming to use genetic instructions (in the form of DNA or RNA) for a coronavirus protein that prompts an immune response. The nucleic acid is inserted into human cells, which then churn out copies of the virus protein; most of these vaccines encode the virus's spike protein.

RNA- and DNA-based vaccines are safe and easy to develop: to produce them involves making genetic material only, not the virus. But they are unproven: no licensed vaccines use this technology.

[Callaway, 2020](#)

DNA

COVID-19 Vaccine developer/manufacturer	Type of Candidate Vaccine	Clinical Stage			
		Phase 1	Phase 1/2	Phase 2	Phase 3
Inovio Pharmaceuticals (USA)/ International Vaccine Institute (South Korea)	DNA plasmid vaccine with electroporation (INO-4800)	NCT04336410	NCT04447781	-	-
Osaka University (Japan)/ AnGes/ Takara Bio	DNA plasmid vaccine + Adjuvant (AG0301-COVID19)	-	NCT04463472	-	-
Zydus Cadila (part of Cadila Healthcare Limited, in India)	DNA plasmid vaccine (NCOV 1002 Version 02, ZyCoV-D)	-	-	CTR1/2020/07/026352	-
Genexine Consortium (Genexine, Binex, GenNBio, International Vaccine Institute, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology and Pohang University of Science and Technology)	DNA Vaccine (GX-19)	-	NCT04445389	-	-

RNA

COVID-19 Vaccine developer/manufacturer	Type of Candidate Vaccine	Clinical Stage			
		Phase 1	Phase 1/2	Phase 2	Phase 3
Moderna/NIAID	mRNA-1273 is a lipid nanoparticle–encapsulated, nucleoside-modified messenger RNA (mRNA)–based vaccine that encodes the SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein stabilized in its prefusion conformation	NCT04283461, Interim Report	-		NCT04470427
BioNTech/Fosun Pharma/Pfizer	BNT162, a lipid nanoparticle-formulated, nucleoside-modified mRNA vaccine that encodes trimerized SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein receptor-binding domain (RBD). Three doses tested	-	2020-001038-36, ChiCTR2000034825	-	NCT04368728
	BNT162b1	-	Study Report	-	-
Arcturus/Duke-NUS	STARR™ mRNA, ARCT-021	-	NCT04480957	-	-
Imperial College London funded by Medical Research Council and UK Research and Innovation	A purified synthetic chemical called mRNA which mimics the virus gene for a spike protein on its surface. LNP-nCoVsaRNA (lipid nanoparticle formulated, nucleoside-modified, self-amplifying ribonucleic acid (saRNA) vaccine encoding the S glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2	ISRCTN17072692	-	-	-
Curevac collaborating with the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI)	CVnCoV (lipid-nanoparticle (LNP)-formulated mRNA vaccine)	NCT04449276	-	-	-
People's Liberation Army (PLA), Academy of Military Sciences/Walvax Biotech.	ARCoV, a novel coronavirus Messenger RNA (mRNA)	ChiCTR2000034112	-	-	-

Data source: [draft landscape of COVID-19 vaccine candidates](#), press releases, and companies websites

Viral-Vector and Protein-Based Vaccines

VIRAL-VECTOR VACCINES

Around 25 groups say they are working on viral-vector vaccines. A virus such as measles or adenovirus is genetically engineered so that it can produce coronavirus proteins in the body. These viruses are weakened so they cannot cause disease. There are two types: those that can still replicate within cells and those that cannot because key genes have been disabled.

Replicating viral vector (such as weakened measles)

The newly approved Ebola vaccine is an example of a viral-vector vaccine that replicates within cells. Such vaccines tend to be safe and provoke a strong immune response. Existing immunity to the vector could blunt the vaccine's effectiveness, however.

Non-replicating viral vector (such as adenovirus)

No licensed vaccines use this method, but they have a long history in gene therapy. Booster shots can be needed to induce long-lasting immunity. US-based drug giant Johnson & Johnson is working on this approach.

PROTEIN-BASED VACCINES

Many researchers want to inject coronavirus proteins directly into the body. Fragments of proteins or protein shells that mimic the coronavirus's outer coat can also be used.

Protein subunits

Twenty-eight teams are working on vaccines with viral protein subunits — most of them are focusing on the virus's spike protein or a key part of it called the receptor binding domain. Similar vaccines against the SARS virus protected monkeys against infection but haven't been tested in people. To work, these vaccines might require adjuvants — immune-stimulating molecules delivered alongside the vaccine — as well as multiple doses.

Virus-like particles

Empty virus shells mimic the coronavirus structure, but aren't infectious because they lack genetic material. Five teams are working on 'virus-like particle' (VLP) vaccines, which can trigger a strong immune response, but can be difficult to manufacture.

Viral-Vector Vaccines

Replicating Viral Vector

COVID-19 Vaccine developer/manufacturer	Type of Candidate Vaccine	Clinical Stage			
		Phase 1	Phase 1/2	Phase 2	Phase 3
Institute Pasteur (France)/Themis (subsidiary of Merck) /Univ. of Pittsburg CVR/Merck Sharp & Dohme (USA)	Measles vector vaccine engineered to express SARS-CoV-2 proteins on its surface (V591)	NCT04497298			

Non-Replicating Viral Vector

COVID-19 Vaccine developer/manufacturer	Type of Candidate Vaccine	Clinical Stage			
		Phase 1	Phase 1/2	Phase 2	Phase 3
University of Oxford/AstraZeneca	Adenovirus-vectored vaccine (ChAdOx1 nCoV-19) expressing the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein	-	2020-001072-15 , PACTR202006922165132 , Interim Report	2020-001228-32	ISRCTN89951424
CanSino Biological Inc./Beijing Institute of Biotechnology	A recombinant adenovirus type-5 (Ad5) vectored COVID-19 vaccine expressing SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein	ChiCTR2000030906 , Study Report	-	ChiCTR2000030906 , Study Report	-
Janssen Pharmaceutical Companies	Adenovirus serotype 26 (Ad26) vector-based vaccines expressing the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in nonhuman primates	-	NCT04436276 , Study Report	-	-
Gamaleya Research Institute of Epidemiology and Microbiology, Health Ministry of the Russian Federation (in collaboration with Acellena Contract Drug Research and Development)	A recombinant adenovirus vector based on the human adenovirus type 26 and type 5 expressing SARS-CoV-2 spike protein	NCT04436471 , NCT04437875	-	-	-
ReiThera(Italy)/LEUKOCARE(Germany)/Univercells (Belgium)	A novel replication-incompetent simian adenovirus strain, encoding the full-length Spike (S) protein of SARS-CoV-2. The vaccine candidate is called GRAd-COV2	2020-002835-31 to start soon	-	-	-

Data source: [draft landscape of COVID-19 vaccine candidates](#), press releases, and companies websites

Protein-based vaccines

Protein Subunit

COVID-19 Vaccine developer/manufacturer	Type of Candidate Vaccine	Clinical Stage			
		Phase 1	Phase 1/2	Phase 2	Phase 3
Anhui Zhifei Longcom Biopharmaceutical/Institute of Microbiology, Chinese Academy of Sciences collaborators, The Second Affiliated Hospital of Chongqing Medical University, Beijing Chao Yang Hospital	Adjuvanted recombinant protein (RBD-Dimer) (CHO Cell)	NCT04445194	-	NCT04466085	-
Novavax (USA)	NVX-CoV2373 is a full length recombinant SARS CoV- 2 glycoprotein nanoparticle vaccine adjuvanted with Matrix M	-	NCT04368988	-	-
Kentucky Bioprocessing, Inc (subsidiary of British American Tobacco)	Receptor binding domain of the Spike protein produced in tobacco. Plant-based vaccine.	-	NCT04473690	-	-
Clover Biopharmaceuticals Inc.(China)/GSK/Dynavax	Native like Trimeric subunit Spike Protein vaccine (SCB-2019 with AS03 adjuvant and CpG 1018 adjuvant plus Alum adjuvant	NCT04405908, Interim Report	-	-	-
Vaxine Pty Ltd(Australia)/Medytox (Korea)	Recombinant spike protein with Advax™ adjuvant (COVAX-19®)	NCT04453852	-	-	-
University of Queensland/Commonwealth Serum Laboratories (CSL)/Seqirus (subsidiary of CSL)	Molecular clamp stabilized Spike protein with MF59 adjuvant	ACTRN12620000674932p	-	-	-
Medigen Vaccine Biologics Corporation (Taiwan)/NIAID/Dynavax	S-2P protein + CpG 1018 (MVC-COV1901)	NCT04487210	-	-	-

Virus Like Particle (VLP)

COVID-19 Vaccine developer/manufacturer	Type of Candidate Vaccine	Clinical Stage			
		Phase 1	Phase 1/2	Phase 2	Phase 3
Medicago Inc. (Canada) collaborating with GSK and Dynavax	Plant-derived VLP unadjuvanted or adjuvanted with either CpG 1018 or AS03	NCT04450004			

Searching for mRNA vaccine inventions

Knowns and unknowns about searching for mRNA vaccine related patents

Six of the 29 vaccine candidates currently in clinical trial evaluation to prevent COVID-19 are mRNA vaccines: mRNA-1273 (Moderna/NIAID), BNT-162 (BioNTech/Fosun Pharma/Pfizer), ARCT-021 (Arcturus/Duke-NUS), LNP-nCoVsaRNA (Imperial College London), CVnCoV (CureVac), and ARCoV (PLA/Walvax Biotech). Recently, [Cecilia Martin and Drew Lowery (CMDL)](<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41573-020-00119-8>), updated an IP landscape on mRNA vaccines covering 4 of the six vaccine candidates and published a list of 113 INPADOC patent families containing claims restricted to vaccines encoded by mRNA. We extracted these patents and created a public Lens collection, [SARS-CoV-2: mRNA vaccines-CMDL](<https://link.lens.org/l98CUEoHBKf>) to enable readers to explore it in Lens.org, recreate it in their work area, analyze it further with dashboards.

An added feature for the Lens users is that they can link that collection to the query to make it a dynamic collection that gets updated with each with new data release. To do so, we reconstructed the CMDL search strategy in the Lens to help users in this process. The published search strategy was: (ribonucleic acid or RNA or messenger ribonucleic acid or mRNA or messenger RNA) NEAR5 (vaccin*) which means that authors looked for patents in title, abstracts, or claims fields that have variants of mRNA term AND within 5 words of Vaccin*.

In Lens.org, the symbol tilde ~ is equivalent to the "NEAR" operator. Using this example, I describe below some of the variations on the search strategy which can be performed in addition to repeating the CMDL one, when trying to discover inventions on the topic.

Reconstructing the CMDL search strategy. Date: August 17.

1. Search in title, abstract, Claims (title:("ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5) OR abstract:("ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5) OR claims:("ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5)) OR (title:("RNA vaccin"~5) OR abstract:("RNA vaccin"~5) OR claims:("RNA vaccin"~5)) OR (title:("messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5) OR abstract:("messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5) OR claims:("messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5)) OR (title:("mRNA vaccin"~5) OR abstract:("mRNA vaccin"~5) OR claims:("mRNA vaccin"~5)) OR (title:("messenger RNA vaccin"~5) OR abstract:("messenger RNA vaccin"~5) OR claims:("messenger RNA vaccin"~5))

Search results: 1,846 patent documents (565) patent simple families or inventions.

The search can be accessed at <https://link.lens.org/E07dpWvy1Sg>.

Lens users can save this query and set alerts to receive updates.

2. Search in all fields including full text (Broad search) "ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5 OR "RNA vaccin"~5 OR "messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5 OR "mRNA vaccin"~5 OR "messenger RNA vaccin"~5

Search results: 14,731 patent documents (4,482 inventions) The search can be accessed at <https://link.lens.org/MG5qqbofLwf>

3. Search in claims (narrow search) claims:("ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5) OR claims:("RNA vaccin"~5) OR claims:("messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin"~5) OR claims:("mRNA vaccin"~5) OR claims:("messenger RNA vaccin"~5)

Search results: 976 patent documents (452 patent families) The search can be accessed at <https://link.lens.org/i4AYWe73F2d>

The above searches allow up to 5 word distance between mRNA variants and the root word vaccin. What if one is interested in all patents that have exactly those phrases without allowing any added words, then the searches would be:

4. Searching all fields: "ribonucleic acid vaccin" OR "RNA vaccin" OR "messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin" OR "mRNA vaccin" OR "messenger RNA vaccin"

Search results: 3,727 patent documents (1,155 patent families) The search can be accessed at <https://link.lens.org/otSj4AGGonj>

5. Searching in title, abstract, claims: (title:("ribonucleic acid vaccin") OR abstract:("ribonucleic acid vaccin") OR claims:("ribonucleic acid vaccin")) OR (title:("RNA vaccin") OR abstract:("RNA vaccin") OR claims:("RNA vaccin")) OR (title:("messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin") OR abstract:("messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin") OR claims:("messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin")) OR (title:("mRNA vaccin") OR abstract:("mRNA vaccin") OR claims:("mRNA vaccin")) OR (title:("messenger RNA vaccin") OR abstract:("messenger RNA vaccin") OR claims:("messenger RNA vaccin"))

Search results: 488 patent documents (115 patent families) The search can be accessed at <https://link.lens.org/RJPcmvJwNjj>

6. Searching in claims: claims:("ribonucleic acid vaccin") OR claims:("RNA vaccin") OR claims:("messenger ribonucleic acid vaccin") OR claims:("mRNA vaccin") OR claims:("messenger RNA vaccin")

Search results: 157 patent documents (71 patent families) The search can be accessed at <https://link.lens.org/3KciQPxhoKi>

All the 6 searches can be made into collections and explored either by analytic dashboard or filtered further by other fields or classification codes to refine and focus the dataset on the most relevant documents (inventions) that will be manually analyzed in a dynamic and interactive Lens report.

Comparing collections based on searches in the claims for either patents with works mRNA variants adjacent to or up to 5 words from the word vaccin* (mRNA vaccin-claims and mRNA vaccin~5-claims) can reveal trends of patent citations over time and inform about different applicants or inventors.

patent citations in mRNAvaccin-claims collection

[View as Lens result](#)

Patent citations in mRNAvaccin~5-claims collection

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Top applicants in mRNAvaccin-claims collection

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Top applicants in the mRNAvaccin~5-claims collection

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Top inventors in mRNAvaccin-claims collection

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Drug, Biological, and Dietary Supplement Interventions

Several therapeutic interventions, which can inhibit virus entry and/or replication of SARS-CoV-2 in-vitro or in animal models have been identified, but such results need to be translated into effective therapies in humans. Recently, The World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO-ICTRP) has begun live mapping of ongoing research to monitor in real-time any new evidence that becomes available for treating and preventing Covid-19. Examining >300 clinical trials in the USA revealed that most treatments seem to be on palliative and supportive care. Considering the catastrophic impact of COVID-19 on our public health system, emergency use of some of these therapies have already been permitted prior to any clinical trial. Investigative efforts continue to identify new or fine tune old therapies as our understanding of the basic virology of this virus and its interaction with the host are clearer. Zooming on the 107 clinical trials that are recruiting at this stage (August 18, 2020), we list below the drug, biological, and dietary supplement interventions that are at various clinical trial phases and present the two most prophylactic treatments considered at this stage. Data source: [US National Library of Medicine, Clinicaltrials.gov](https://www.clinicaltrials.gov).

Drug Interventions with contributions from industry (13), others (64), and combined efforts (13).

Drug interventions	Title	Sponsor/Collaborators	Phases
NA-831 and Remdesivir (GS-5734) (Inhaled Nanoparticle Formulation and different combinations)	Safety, Tolerability and Pharmacokinetics of Inhaled Nanoparticle Formulation of Remdesivir (GS-5734) and NA-831	NeuroActiva, Inc.	1
NA-831, Atazanavir and Dexamethasone Combination Therapy	NA-831, Atazanavir and Dexamethasone Combination Therapy for the Treatment of COVID-19 Infection	NeuroActiva, Inc.	2 & 3
EIDD-2801a (an orally bioavailable NHC prodrug (β -D-N4-hydroxycytidine-5'-isopropyl ester))	A Safety, Tolerability and Efficacy of EIDD-2801 to Eliminate Infectious Virus Detection in Persons With COVID-19	Ridgeback Biotherapeutics, LP	2
Abidol hydrochloride; Abidol Hydrochloride combined with Interferon atomization	A Prospective/Retrospective, Randomized Controlled Clinical Study of Interferon Atomization in the 2019-nCoV Pneumonia	Tongji Hospital	4
Abidol hydrochloride; Oseltamivir; Lopinavir/ritonavir	A Prospective/Retrospective, Randomized Controlled Clinical Study of Antiviral Therapy in the 2019-nCoV Pneumonia	Tongji Hospital	4
Apilimod Dimesylate Capsule; Other: Placebo	A Study of LAM-002A for the Prevention of Progression of COVID-19	AI Therapeutics, Inc.; Yale University	2
Azithromycin; Hydroxychloroquine; Lopinavir	OUTpatient Treatment of COVID-19 in Patients With Risk Factor for Poor Outcome	Groupe Hospitalier Paris Saint Joseph	3
Baricitinib; Hydroxychloroquine; Placebo Administration	Baricitinib, Placebo and Antiviral Therapy for the Treatment of Patients With Moderate and Severe COVID-19	University of Southern California; National Cancer Institute (NCI)	2
BLD-2660 (a synthetic, orally active, small molecule inhibitor of calpain (CAPN) 1, 2, and 9)	Safety and Antiviral Activity of BLD-2660 in COVID-19 Hospitalized Subjects	Blade Therapeutics; Clinipace Worldwide	2
Brazilian Green Propolis Extract (EPP-AF); Other: Standard care	The Use of Brazilian Green Propolis Extract (EPP-AF) in Patients Affected by COVID-19.	D'Or Institute for Research and Education; Hospital Sao Rafael	2 & 3
Brequinar; Other: Standard of Care	Safety and Anti-coronavirus Response of Suppression of Host Nucleotide Synthesis in Patients With COVID-19	Clear Creek Bio, Inc.	1 & 2
Chloroquine or Hydroxychloroquine; Lopinavir/Ritonavir; Other: Best standard of care; Rivaroxaban; Thromboprophylaxis; Candesartan; non-RAS blocking antihypertensives; Clazakizumab; placebo for clazakizumab	Austrian CoronaVirus Adaptive Clinical Trial (COVID-19)	Medical University of Vienna; Kaiser Franz Josef Hospital; SMZ-Ost Donauspital; Otto Wagner Hospital; Hospital Hietzing; Wilhelminenspital Vienna; Medical University Innsbruck	2 & 3

For a full view of the table see the live version of this report at <https://link.lens.org/BlwEkPFpOJh>

Biological Interventions

Biological Interventions	Title	Sponsor/Collaborators	Phases
BCG vaccine (Freeze-dried)	BCG Vaccine in Reducing Morbidity and Mortality in Elderly Individuals in COVID-19 Hotspots	Tuberculosis Research Centre, India; ICMR-National Institute for Research in Tuberculosis, Chennai, Tamil Nadu; All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi; National Institute for Research in Environmental Health, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh; National Institute of Occupational Health, Ahmedabad, Gujarat; King Edward Memorial Hospital; National Institute for Implementation Research on Non-Communicable Disease	3
BNT162a1; BNT162b1; BNT162b2; BNT162c2	A Trial Investigating the Safety and Effects of Four BNT162 Vaccines Against COVID-2019 in Healthy Adults	BioNTech RNA Pharmaceuticals GmbH; BioNTech SE	1 & 2
Convalescent plasma	Convalescent Plasma Therapy in Severe COVID-19 Infection	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Dhaka Medical College	2
CONVALESCENT PLASMA	Transfusion of Convalescent Plasma for the Early Treatment of Patients With COVID-19	Azienda Ospedaliero, Universitaria Pisana	2
Convalescent Plasma	Safety in Convalescent Plasma Transfusion to COVID-19	Hospital San Jose Tec de Monterrey; Tecnologico de Monterrey	1
Convalescent Plasma	COVID-19 Convalescent Plasma Treatment in SARS-CoV-2 Infected Patients	Ministry of Health, Kuwait	1
Convalescent Plasma of patients with COVID-19; Other: placebo (hartmann plus albumine)	Convalescent Plasma of Covid-19 to Treat SARS-CoV-2 a Randomized Doble Blind 2 Center Trial	Grupo Mexicano para el Estudio de la Medicina Intensiva; Hospital General Naval de Alta Especialidad - Escuela Medico Naval; National Institute of Pediatrics, Mexico; Instituto Nacional de Enfermedades Respiratorias	2
COVID-19 Convalescent Plasma	Early transfusion of Convalescent Plasma in Elderly COVID-19 Patients. to Prevent Disease Progression.	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS	2 & 3
CYNK-001	Natural Killer Cell (CYNK-001) Infusions in Adults With COVID-19 (CYNK-001-COVID-19)	Celularity Incorporated; IDRI; Lung Biotechnology PBC; California Institute for Regenerative Medicine (CIRM)	1 & 2
Mesenchymal stem cells; Other: Placebo	Mesenchymal Stem Cell Infusion for COVID-19 Infection	Dr. Zaineb Akram; National Institute of Blood and Marrow Transplant (NIBMT), Pakistan	2
Mesenchymal stromal cells	Mesenchymal Stromal Cell Therapy for Severe Covid-19 Infection	University of Liege	1 & 2
Plasma; Other: Best Available Therapy	Convalescent Plasma Compared to the Best Available Therapy for the Treatment of SARS-CoV-2 Pneumonia	Hospital Universitario Dr. Jose E. Gonzalez	2
Remestemcel-L; Drug: Placebo	MSCs in COVID-19 ARDS	Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai; Mesoblast, Inc.	3
SARILUMAB	Sarilumab for Patients With Moderate COVID-19 Disease	Westyn Branch-Elliman; VA Boston Healthcare System	2
TY027; Other: 0.9% Saline	Safety of TY027, a Treatment for COVID-19, in Humans	Tychan Pte Ltd.	1

Dietary Supplement Interventions

Dietary Supplement Interventions	Title	Sponsor/Collaborators	Phases
Honey; Nigella Sativa / Black Cumin; Placebos	Honey & Nigella Sativa Trial Against COVID-19	Sohaib Ashraf; Sheikh Zayed Federal Postgraduate Medical Institute	3
Natural Honey; Other: Standard Care	Efficacy of Natural Honey Treatment in Patients With Novel Coronavirus	Misr University for Science and Technology	3
Nigella sativa	Nigella Sativa in COVID-19	King Abdulaziz University	2

Data Sources

What is the evidence behind this report?

[SARS-CoV-2: Spike protein](#)

- SCHOLARLY_WORK COLLECTION
- Items: [1,930](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 7, 2020
- Updated: Aug 13, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Recombination and mutation](#)

- SCHOLARLY_WORK COLLECTION
- Items: [56](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 9, 2020
- Updated: Aug 17, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Spike D614G](#)

- SCHOLARLY_WORK COLLECTION
- Items: [48](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 10, 2020
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[SARS-CoV-2: Therapeutic candidates](#)

- SCHOLARLY_WORK COLLECTION
- Items: [12](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 13, 2020
- Updated: Aug 15, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Neutralizing antibodies](#)

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- Created: Aug 13, 2020
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[SARS-CoV-2: Genetic variants](#)

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- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
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[SARS-CoV-2: Viral quasispecies](#)

- SCHOLARLY_WORK COLLECTION
- Items: [8](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 15, 2020
- Updated: Aug 15, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2:mRA vaccine patents \(Lens\)](#)

- PATENT COLLECTION
- Items: [261](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 18, 2020
- Updated: Aug 18, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Cell entry](#)

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- Items: [127](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 17, 2020
- Updated: Aug 17, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2:mRNA vaccin-Claims](#)

- PATENT COLLECTION
- Items: [157](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 18, 2020

- Updated: Aug 18, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2:mRNAvaccin~5-Claims](#)

- PATENT COLLECTION
- Items: [976](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 18, 2020
- Updated: Aug 18, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Spike protein](#)

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- Items: [48](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 7, 2020
- Updated: Aug 7, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Spike protein](#)

- SCHOLARLY_WORK COLLECTION
- Items: [1,930](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 7, 2020
- Updated: Aug 13, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Broad](#)

- SCHOLARLY_WORK COLLECTION
- Items: [15,294](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 8, 2020
- Updated: Aug 8, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Therapeutic agents](#)

- PATENT COLLECTION
- Items: [14](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 9, 2020
- Updated: Aug 9, 2020

[SARS-CoV-2: Recombination and mutation](#)

- SCHOLARLY_WORK COLLECTION
- Items: [56](#)
- Curator: Osmat A. Jefferson ...
- Created: Aug 9, 2020
- Updated: Aug 17, 2020

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